

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TO MANOBO LEARNERS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The current study presents the English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners as experienced by the teacher participants. This study envisions to getting into the core of English Language Teaching as experienced by teachers since they are sufficiently knowledgeable about the topic under investigation. To arrive at the description of ELT to Manobo learners, Face-to-Face interview was utilized with six participants from Kalamansig, Lebak, and Palimbang which are municipalities of Sultan Kudarat. For the data analysis, qualitative framework was utilized following the Colaizzi (1978) strategy of descriptive phenomenological data analysis. From the shared experiences, twenty-three (38) subthemes emerged and are further grouped according to their relevance which resulted in nine (9) themes serving as the description of the ELT to Manobo learners. The nine (9) themes are: Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers, Learners' context as characterized by teachers, Significant encounter of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo, Effective teaching strategies for Manobo learners, Culturally responsive teaching, Resourcefulness in remote teaching, Teachers' motivation in teaching, Resilient teaching, and Purposeful teaching. To arrive at the essence of ELT to Manobo learners, the nine themes were thoroughly analyzed which resulted in three (3) emergent themes. These are: Manobo learners learning English language, English teachers teaching English to Manobo learners, and Teachers' Aspirations.

Keywords: *Teachers' aspirations, Culturally responsive teaching, English language teaching, IPEd teachers, Manobo learners, Learner-based teaching*

INTRODUCTION

This section contains the Statement of the Problem, Significance of the Study, Scope and Limitations, and Related Literature and Studies, all essential components in comprehending the research endeavor.

English Language Teaching (ELT) has become a vital aspect of education worldwide, providing individuals with the skills to engage in global communication and access broader opportunities. However, the success of ELT programs is often influenced by learners' linguistic and cultural backgrounds. This research focuses on English Language Teaching to Manobo learners as experienced by teachers through a phenomenological lens.

The Manobo people, one of the main indigenous groups in the Philippines, have a rich cultural heritage and distinct linguistic traditions. Their native languages, which include various Manobo dialects, are central to their identity and way of life. As globalization shapes educational practices, integrating English language education into the Manobo community presents both opportunities and challenges.

In Philippines, the rights of Indigenous Peoples (IPs) to basic education are protected in the 1987 Constitution, the Indigenous Peoples Rights Act (IPRA) of 1997, and international accords such as the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). Meeting the educational needs of IP communities aligns with the Department of Education's (DepEd) commitment to achieving the nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Education for All (EFA) targets. By 2019, the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) program was implemented across 16 regions and 117 divisions, including in Sultan Kudarat division from DepEd SOCCSKSARGEN. Kalamansig, Lebak, and Palimbang from Sultan Kudarat Province are among the municipalities that have successfully implemented the said program.

In English Language Teaching, nurturing a learning environment that will promote English competence among learners is imperative. Techniques such as language immersion and contextualized learning can enhance students' language skills. Extracurricular activities like drama, debates, and public speaking further develop language proficiency alongside critical thinking and communication skills. The use of technology also offers significant advantages in the ELT process.

Moreover, several teaching strategies have been developed to address the needs of non-native speakers, including Manobo learners. These strategies focus on understanding the learners' context, creating a supportive learning environment, and simplifying language instruction. While these align with DepEd's goal of enhancing English language literacy, IPEd teachers face considerable challenges due to various constraints affecting the indigenous learners' language competence (Saysi et al., 2022).

A study conducted in Davao del Sur revealed difficulties faced by teachers instructing Manobo students. Teachers highlighted challenges such as poor grammar,

limited vocabulary, and comprehension issues. The lack of language use outside the classroom further compounded these difficulties. Teachers also faced cultural challenges, as many were unfamiliar with the students' dialect and culture (Cabal, 2017).

Also, Saysi et al. (2022) highlighted the challenges faced by IPEd teachers in improving students' digital literacy, reading comprehension, and writing abilities, as well as adapting lessons to local contexts. These challenges were intensified by inconsistencies in language learning standards, limited instructional resources, varying literacy levels among students, and the instructional approaches employed by teachers.

On a global scale, ELT for Indigenous Peoples has garnered attention in research as nations strive to provide education for all. In the Philippines, a country with over 17 million indigenous peoples from 110 ethnolinguistic groups, studies on ELT for indigenous learners remain limited. A recent study by Lumontod & Pradia (2023) examined the attitudes and challenges faced by Manobo students in learning English. However, little research has focused on ELT from the teachers' perspective.

This study envisions to getting into the core of English Language Teaching to Manobo learners as experienced by teachers since they are sufficiently knowledgeable about the topic under investigation. It is important to highlight that Manobo learners are the group of indigenous learners with a significant number in the area where this research took place. Their substantial presence makes understanding effective English language teaching methods for this community not just academically interesting but practically essential. By studying how teachers successfully adapt their approaches for Manobo learners, we gain valuable insights that can directly benefit many learners. This research responds to a real educational need rather than an abstract academic interest, bridging the gap between teaching frameworks and the lived classroom experiences of teachers.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This section includes reading explaining foundational concepts crucial for comprehending the research undertaking.

Education in Philippines

The Philippine educational system has undergone significant changes over time. In 2012, the Department of Education (DepEd) transitioned to the K-12 curriculum, a 13-year program that spans from Kindergarten to Grade 12. This system, which is legally mandated, gives students the option to pursue higher education upon completion. Starting next school year, the DepEd will introduce a new curriculum called the MATATAG Curriculum (MATATAG Curriculum Pilot, 2023) to address challenges faced by the educational system.

Also, Philippines uses both English and Filipino as the primary mediums of instruction. However, given the country's archipelagic nature, with more than 7,000 islands and over 100 languages, teaching English poses additional challenges. The

diversity of languages spoken across the nation adds complexity to English Language Teaching (ELT).

In another view, Tuguic and Bilan (2023) describe how the onset of virtual learning in the Philippines was prompted by the pandemic and other unforeseen disasters, comparing it to an unwelcome guest who has overstayed their visit. As the pandemic disrupted traditional education, institutions adopted online learning methods which are flourishing in our educational landscape now.

Moreover, as emphasized in a 2023 article from BusinessMirror, education plays a vital role in building human capital, which is fundamental to a nation's economic development. By providing individuals with the necessary skills for employment, education serves as a key driver of economic advancement. This is why the government has allocated PHP924.7 billion for education in the 2024 national budget, a 3.3% increase from the previous year, to improve facilities, update learning materials, and expand skills training opportunities.

However, recent assessments have revealed critical shortcomings in the Philippine educational system. The PISA 2022 results show that Filipino students lag behind their global peers by five to six years in educational achievement, particularly in reading literacy (Abella et al., 2023). This learning gap has prompted lawmakers and DepEd to push for reforms aimed at improving education quality (Philippines Education & Labour Report, 2024).

Indigenous Peoples' Education in the Philippines

The Indigenous Peoples Rights Act of 1997 (RA 8371) mandates that all government agencies recognize and support the rights of Indigenous Cultural Communities/Indigenous Peoples (ICCs/IPs). In accordance with this law, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011, which creates the National Indigenous Peoples Education Policy Framework. This framework promotes cooperation among government entities, IP communities, civil society, and other stakeholders to safeguard the educational rights of IP learners. To support these initiatives, the government has established schools in the far-flung zones where many IP communities reside and has incorporated the Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Program into the national education system.

Moreover, there have been numerous government and non-government initiatives aimed at improving education for IPs. However, challenges remain, particularly in sending young indigenous people to urban schools, a method that has shown limited success. Despite efforts, many programs fall short, and effective approaches to educating indigenous populations remain underexplored.

For effective teaching of Katutubo students, educational institutions must adopt a holistic approach that includes understanding their culture and setting high expectations. Schools should be located within or near Katutubo villages, with active community

involvement in school reforms. Wa-Mbaleka (2013) highlights the importance of incorporating the spiritual dimension into the education of Katutubo students, ensuring that their faith in a higher power is supported. However, cultural challenges persist, including the community's emphasis on early marriages, which leads to school dropouts, and the lack of long-term planning, which is essential for educational success.

A global phenomenon of low classroom engagement is also evident among indigenous students. This issue has been observed in various ethnic groups worldwide, such as African, Latin American, and American Indian populations.

Furthermore, studies such as Rabasso and Rabasso (2014) emphasize that state-funded education should be available to all, including indigenous peoples, in a manner that respects their language and culture. Article 14 of the Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (2007) reaffirms this right, advocating for education systems that cater to indigenous languages and cultural practices.

Adaiton et al. (2023) highlight the aspirations of today's IP youth, who see education as a means of overcoming discrimination and improving their communities. Although these youths are empowered and motivated, many still struggle with challenges such as loss of cultural identity due to fears of discrimination in mainstream educational institutions. To address these issues, organizations within schools should support IP students in maintaining their identity and rights.

While the Philippine education system provides support for IP students, they continue to face obstacles in their academic journeys. Indigenous students tend to have lower enrollment, higher dropout rates, and lower literacy levels than their non-indigenous counterparts. These challenges highlight the need for further efforts to improve retention and completion rates among IP learners (Adaiton et al., 2023).

Manobo Tribe

The Manobo people, an Indigenous group in the Philippines, primarily reside in the southern region of Mindanao. The Manobo consist of diverse subgroups, each characterized by unique languages and cultural practices. The term "Manobo" means "people" or "person," with variations like Manuvu and Minuvu also in use. The name may have originated from the word "Mansuba," which combines "man" (person) and "suba" (river) (Ceria, 2018). The Manobo are believed to have descended from one of the earliest waves of Austronesian migration, preceding other groups like the Ifugao of Luzon. Although the Manobo are considered part of a larger supergroup, including groups such as Bagobo, Hiligaynon, and Bukidnon, some are classified differently.

According to Lumontod and Pradia (2023), Manobo communities are typically found near small lakes or clearings in the forest, living in villages with around four to twelve houses. They rely on slash-and-burn agriculture. As of 2000, the Manobo made up only 5.37% of the household population in Sultan Kudarat Province, which is

predominantly inhabited by Ilonggos, based on data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA).

English Language Teaching

In the modern global context, proficiency in English is essential for both personal and professional advancement. As the dominant language in international business, science, and communication, fluency in English provides access to a wide range of opportunities (Guilherme, 2007). Schools and language centers recognize this and focus on enhancing students' English skills through various methods. Several strategies have been developed to improve English language proficiency.

One key approach is creating an immersive language-learning environment. Immersive programs, where students actively use English in everyday situations, have proven to be highly effective in building language skills (Lan, 2020). Programs like language exchanges, English-speaking clubs, and language camps offer learners with excellent chances to improve their abilities in speaking, listening, reading, and writing in English. These activities help enhance both their confidence and proficiency in the language.

In resource-limited settings, technology plays a crucial role in bridging learning gaps. Mbiydzonyuy and Silungwe (2020) explored how online learning, and digital tools can mitigate the disadvantages faced by students in remote areas. Sun et al. (2024) further investigated how ICT-mediated remote education can transform rural education, emphasizing that access to digital resources significantly improves learning outcomes. This is particularly true nowadays that we are in a generation where technology has improved a thousand folds and learners are adept in using it.

Also, personalized feedback is essential for language development. Akcan and Tatar (2010) emphasize that individual feedback helps students focus on areas that need improvement. Feedback can be delivered through verbal and non-verbal cues, helping students feel recognized and motivated to continue learning. Teachers play a crucial role in providing tailored feedback to address each student's specific needs.

According to Aimen et al. (2024), mastering English is not just a skill but a transformative tool for navigating today's interconnected world. Students often face challenges such as fear of making mistakes, limited vocabulary, and lack of confidence, which can hinder their progress. These psychological barriers, if addressed, can greatly improve their ability to communicate in English.

Finally, giving students opportunities to practice English outside the classroom enhances language proficiency. Participating in extracurricular activities like drama clubs, debate teams, and public speaking competitions helps students apply their language skills in real-world scenarios (Yol & Yoon, 2020). These activities enhance English proficiency while also fostering critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills. A

comprehensive approach that combines classroom instruction, technological tools, and extracurricular experiences can effectively boost students' English language skills.

Experiences of English Language Teachers Teaching Indigenous Learners

Sahoo (2022) conducted a study on English teachers working with Indian tribal students, revealing common challenges such as students' difficulties in understanding English words, poor reading and writing skills, and high rates of absenteeism due to students helping their families at home. These challenges are similar to those faced by educators in other parts of the world.

For instance, Haufiku et al. (2022) found that teachers in Namibia also struggled with limited resources, overcrowded classrooms, lack of parental involvement, and students' negative attitudes toward English learning. This calls for the need for localized instructional materials to make learning relevant and meaningful for indigenous students. UNESCO (2019) also emphasizes the importance of preserving indigenous languages in education, advocating for the integration of indigenous cultural elements into language instruction.

Also, pronunciation remains a key obstacle for indigenous learners. Lado's (1957) Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis posits that the degree of difficulty in acquiring a second language (L2) is largely influenced by the differences between the learner's first language (L1) and the L2, particularly in phonological structures. The greater the disparity between the two sound systems, the more challenging it is for learners to master L2 pronunciation. This claim is supported by subsequent research. Flege (1995) emphasizes that L2 learners experience perceptual and production difficulties when encountering sounds absent from their L1. Similarly, Best and Tyler (2007) argue that unfamiliar L2 phonemes are often assimilated into existing L1 categories, leading to persistent errors.

Harmer (2007) and Richards and Renandya (2022) emphasize the value of interactive and communicative methods in English Language Teaching. They argue that meaningful interaction helps learners develop both fluency and confidence in using the language. In reality, students tend to engage more and perform better when lessons involve real-life communication and collaboration. These methods also encourage active participation, which is often lacking in traditional, teacher-centered classrooms. Clearly, communicative teaching strategies are not just effective—they are essential in promoting deeper language learning.

Furthermore, Bista (2010) and Cook (2010) discuss the role of code-switching as a facilitative tool in multilingual classrooms. Cummins (2000) argues that translation strategies support bilingual learners by connecting new concepts to familiar linguistic structures. These strategies are needed in the process of ELT to Manobo to ensure understanding and transfer of knowledge and it also highlights the necessity of allowing indigenous learners to use their native language as a scaffold for English proficiency.

In the Philippines, Cabal (2017) explored the experiences of English teachers working with Manobo students in Davao del Sur. Teachers reported difficulties such as poor grammar, limited vocabulary, and poor comprehension among students. Language retention was another challenge, as Manobo students did not use English outside the classroom. Teachers also expressed frustration over their own lack of knowledge about the Manobo language and culture, which hindered their ability to connect with students.

Moreover, Gay (2010, 2018) asserts that culturally responsive teaching, which integrates students' cultural backgrounds into the learning process, enhances both engagement and retention. This perspective underscores the importance of acknowledging learners' identities as part of effective instruction. When teaching connects with students' lived experiences and values, it becomes more meaningful and impactful. Such an approach also fosters a more inclusive and respectful classroom environment. Clearly, cultural relevance is not merely beneficial—it is essential to sustaining student interest and improving learning outcomes.

Also, Hammond (2015) notes in her work on culturally responsive teaching with indigenous populations, "the most significant transformation must first happen within the teacher". This transformation is evident in how teachers describe developing specific qualities through their work with Manobo learners, suggesting that the teaching experience promotes what could be termed cultural pedagogical humility.

On the other hand, Robiños et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of teachers' commitment to supporting students from indigenous communities, such as the Mangyan, by fostering an inclusive learning environment. Teachers in their study stressed that recognizing each student's uniqueness and nurturing a deep understanding of their background were key to making education meaningful. They promoted equal respect and attention for all students, irrespective of their cultural or ethnic backgrounds, to ensure an inclusive and supportive learning environment.

In a study of Lumontod and Pradia (2023) which had Manobo learners as their participants, the learners reported feelings of marginalization and difficulty connecting their indigenous identity with the language being taught. The study emphasized the importance of integrating cultural context into instruction to improve both comprehension and learner confidence. It also highlighted that culturally inclusive practices foster a stronger sense of belonging among indigenous students. Their findings call for more empathetic, context-sensitive language teaching strategies in multicultural classrooms.

Teachers play a pivotal role in creating supportive learning environments for indigenous students. Jennings and Greenberg (2009) stress the importance of teacher social and emotional competence in promoting positive student outcomes. They argue that teachers who regulate their emotions effectively are better equipped to manage classroom challenges and build trusting relationships with students. Noddings (2012) and Day (2004) highlight the emotional and psychological resilience required for teaching in marginalized communities.

Noddings (2012) also emphasizes the ethics of care in education, asserting that genuine concern for students' well-being forms the foundation of effective teaching, while Day (2004) points out that sustained commitment and moral purpose are essential for navigating the complexities of underserved classrooms. Schunk (2012) reinforces that students' motivation and engagement are directly linked to their teachers' attitudes and commitment. He further notes that teachers who demonstrate enthusiasm and belief in students' abilities can significantly enhance learners' self-efficacy and academic performance.

Moreover, appreciation and positive feedback from students and the community reflect a deep sense of respect, making the teacher feel valued. According to Nalipay et al. (2019), such emotional feedback plays a significant role in maintaining teacher resilience, particularly in culturally diverse settings. They add that this kind of feedback strengthens teachers' intrinsic motivation, which is critical for sustaining long-term dedication in multicultural educational contexts.

Despite the challenges, teachers consistently expressed their dedication to helping their indigenous students succeed. They believe in the importance of guiding their students to dream big and improve their lives through education, regardless of cultural or linguistic differences. By fostering a caring, inclusive environment, educators can empower indigenous learners and help them overcome obstacles to academic success.

Moreover, Brunetti (2006) identified teaching perseverance as a key trait among educators working in challenging contexts. His study revealed that teacher resilience is often anchored in a strong sense of moral purpose and a deep commitment to social justice. This aligns with findings that highlight the importance of teachers' long-term goals for their learners. It also reinforces the idea that the effectiveness of the teaching-learning process is closely tied to the dedication and mindset of the teacher. Such insights underscore the vital role of teacher motivation in sustaining educational quality, especially in less favorable conditions.

These insights also align with findings from Bishop and Durksen (2020), who highlighted that effective engagement with Indigenous students requires teachers to possess personal attributes such as patience, flexibility, and empathy. Their research underscores the importance of these qualities in building trust and enhancing educational outcomes for Indigenous learners.

These affirmations from students and the community reflect a deep sense of respect, making the teacher feel valued. According to Nalipay et al. (2019), such emotional feedback plays a significant role in maintaining teacher resilience, particularly in culturally diverse settings. Thus, it takes both of the teachers and learners to flourish in English language teaching.

Theories of Second Language Acquisition

Language acquisition theories provide a foundation for understanding how students, particularly indigenous learners, acquire English. Krashen's (1982) Input

Hypothesis emphasizes the role of comprehensible input in second language learning, stating that learners acquire language when they are exposed to meaningful input slightly beyond their current proficiency level. Similarly, Lightbown and Spada (2013) discuss how exposure and interaction enhance language learning, reinforcing Krashen's claim that language acquisition is best facilitated in natural communication settings.

Vygotsky's (1978) Social Constructivist Theory underscores the importance of social interaction in learning, arguing that cognitive development is largely mediated by cultural and linguistic exchanges. Cummins (2007) extends this argument by advocating for bilingual instructional strategies that support indigenous students' home languages while facilitating English acquisition. These perspectives highlight the necessity of a culturally responsive pedagogy in English language teaching (ELT) for indigenous learners.

Phenomenology in Education

Moran (2000) defines phenomenology as the study of phenomena, with a focus on how they are consciously experienced. In qualitative research, phenomenology explores individuals' lived experiences to uncover the essence of a phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It emphasizes personal knowledge, subjectivity, and the significance of individual perspectives. As noted by Lester (1999), phenomenological research aims to illuminate how phenomena are perceived by individuals in a given situation, offering insights into subjective experiences, motivations, and actions.

Various studies have used phenomenology in qualitative research. For instance, Lubo and Marimon (2020) explored English language challenges faced by Indigenous learners in the Philippines, focusing on vocabulary and expression. Their study involved five Grade 2 Indigenous Peoples (IP) students, utilizing oral evaluations and observations to gather data. Results revealed that due to a lack of English vocabulary, the participants struggled to identify objects in their surroundings.

In a related study, Lumontod and Pradia (2023) used a phenomenological approach to explore the experiences of Manobo learners in studying English. Through interviews with ten participants, they identified key challenges such as language anxiety, limited exposure to English, and lack of culturally responsive teaching.

According to Morse (1997) it suggests that phenomenological studies typically involve at least six participants, while Creswell (1998) recommends limiting the number to ten. This ensures a manageable depth of analysis while capturing a range of experiences.

Descriptive Phenomenology

The descriptive phenomenological approach includes various methodologies developed by researchers such as Giorgi (2009) and Colaizzi (1978). These methods

differ mainly in how they ensure the reliability of results, which refers to the credibility and reliability of research results (Lincoln & Guba, 1986). Giorgi's method involves capturing participants' experiences in their own words without imposing external interpretations, while Colaizzi's seven-step process includes member checking, where findings are reviewed by participants to verify accuracy (Colaizzi, 1978).

Thematic Analysis

This study utilized thematic analysis for evaluating data, following Colaizzi's (1978) strategy of descriptive phenomenological data analysis. The process included familiarizing oneself with the data through transcription and thorough reading, identifying significant responses, formulating meaning for those responses, creating codes, finding cluster of themes, categories and emergent themes, revising and filtering these themes, compiling a report that shows fundamental structure of the phenomenon, and sharing the findings to the participants. The goal is to identify recurring patterns and themes that address the research questions.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe the English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners as experienced by the teachers. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. How may ELT to Manobo learners be described as experienced by teachers?
2. What is the essence of ELT to Manobo learners as experienced by teachers?

METHODOLOGY

This section includes the investigative methodologies employed in the study, encompassing research design, research paradigm, locale of study, map of the locale of study, diagrammatic workflow, participant, research instrument, data collection, data analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

In this research, qualitative research by means of descriptive phenomenology is utilized to describe the English Language Teaching to Manobo learners as experienced by the teachers. This paper used a qualitative approach since the description of ELT as experienced by the teachers could only be best explored and expressed through words in an in-depth face-to-face interview. This process allowed the researcher to acquire rich data for analysis.

Furthermore, the study utilized descriptive phenomenology. A key aspect of this method involves the researcher striving to eliminate personal biases through a process called bracketing. This methodology is suitable for the study since the researcher maintains an objective stance, not being directly engaged with the phenomenon under examination.

Locale of Study

The research is conducted in schools at the three municipalities of Sultan Kudarat Province namely: Kalamansig, Lebak, and Palimbang. The DepEd Sultan Kudarat (SK) Division has a total of 50 schools implementing Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd) Program. The three municipalities are among the municipalities offering IPEd Program within the province. The participating schools are Datu Ina Capitan Integrated School and Datu Bak-Bak Apang Integrated School in Kalamansig Municipality; Tibong-Tibong Integrated School, and Elem Elementary School in Lebak Municipality; and Dumolol Integrated School and Wasag Elementary School- Extension in Palimbang Municipality.

Moreover, the schools that took part in this study are mostly located in the mountainous area of the said municipalities where the Manobo Tribe are usually located. Also, these schools have limited internet access due to the difficulty of internet providers putting up the necessary infrastructure in the mountainous areas which may affect the ELT since most interactive and engaging activities could be found online. Although public WiFi services are currently made available in those areas, its usage still depends on the availability of electricity and weather conditions. Teachers' use of the internet is extremely vital nowadays, from giving engaging activities to students to simplifying lessons on the part of teachers. With their situation, teachers there mostly rely on books and modules in delivering their lessons. Lessons plans are mostly crafted without so much help from websites found online. Computers, laptops, cellphones and other educational gadgets which may aid to the English teaching-learning process are also limited.

There is also a variety of language used in these municipalities because Sultan Kudarat Province is populated with Tri-people (Muslims, Christian, and Lumad). However, most of the people speak and understand Ilonggo language. It is worth noting that the province is dominated by Ilonggos with about 46.92% while Manobo is only about 5.37% of the household population based on Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) as of year 2000.

Participants

This study initially selected 20 teachers that could possibly participate in the face-to-face interview. The teacher included is at least three to four years in service, he/she is handling at least 90% of Manobo learners in a section and is also participating willingly for the study. Those teachers who do not qualify with the basic qualifications mentioned above are automatically excluded from this study. From the 20 teachers initially selected, six are chosen with the most varied demographics. A sampling grid is also utilized to determine those six participants. The sampling grid includes the following details: Teacher Code, Municipality, Gender, Status, School, Ethnicity, Length of Service, and the Percentage of Manobo Students in the section they are handling.

Research Instrument

This study utilized an Interview Guide in conducting face-to-face interviews. This is composed of the interview protocol that is observed throughout the interview. It also contained preliminary questions to know details about the participants which are related to the study such as their length of service in the DepEd and the percentage of Manobo learners in their handled sections. These questions are also raised to establish a connection with the teachers being interviewed. The main course of this Interview Guide is the open-ended questions. The questions were centered on describing English Language Teaching as experienced by the teachers. Building on the teachers' responses, subsequent clarifying inquiries and thorough questions are formulated to elicit deeper and more comprehensive narratives of their experiences. This Interview Guide is validated by a panel of experts, selected professors from Notre Dame of Marbel University (NDMU), before being utilized. They checked the consistency and congruence of questions to the study's statement of the problem. A dry run interview is also done, and a sample transcription is checked by the researcher's adviser to ensure that the proper way of transcribing and doing thematic analysis is followed

Data Collection

In this descriptive-phenomenological study, data was gathered through personal interviews with the participants. Prior to conducting the interview, an approval to conduct the study is sought from the Graduate School of the Notre Dame Marbel University (NDMU) and the NDMU Ethics Review Board (ERB). Next, an approval from the Sultan Kudarat Division Office is also secured. After that, a letter to the school principals of the participating schools is sent. Once approved, the researcher listed the possible participants for the study and with the help of the sampling grid, six teachers are selected.

After selecting the participants, the teachers to be interviewed are contacted. Participants are consulted to determine their most convenient time for participating in the in-person interviews, while also considering the time frame of the study. When the participant and interviewer agreed with a schedule, the face-to-face interview commenced. Participants are informed of the proceedings of the personal interview, and the researcher mentioned the audio recording. The researcher let each participant read the Informed Consent Form. Participants also completed the Participant Agreement Form before proceeding with the interview. In answering the questions, participants are encouraged to speak in the language they are comfortable with for them to share the most out of their experiences. The researcher kept an audio recording of each interview, and a noise free setting is also ensured. Additionally, the researcher focused on establishing a rapport with the interviewee. Every interview with a participant lasted for an average of 30-40 minutes. The researcher stayed in contact with the participant until the completion of the study, which also determined the length of the participant's involvement in this study.

Data Analysis

This process began with the researcher listening to the audio recording to transcribe the interviews with the six participants. Following this, the researcher

thoroughly immersed herself in the transcripts of interviews, carefully understanding each transcript to grasp the complete meaning of the text. Using Colaizzi (1978) method of data analysis, significant responses from the transcripts that pertain to the participants' experiences of English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners is identified, assigned formulated meanings and coding. After that, there is searching for themes or patterns, finding what is common among the descriptions of the participants on ELT to Manobo learners. These patterns or cluster of themes are organized into bigger concepts or themes.

The themes and subthemes are further analyzed to get the essence of the ELT to Manobo learners as experienced by the teachers. The final step involved preparing a report that presents comprehensive analysis of selected excerpts and connects the findings to the research question. When the thematic analysis is completed, the researcher shared the results with the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo Learners as experienced by the teachers. From these experiences, significant responses were extracted and given formulated meanings and initial codes. Next, they are categorized according to their relevance and then clustered into themes and subthemes. These themes and subthemes are given names and are further analyzed to come up with the emergent themes.

English language teaching to Manobo learners as experienced by teachers

English language teaching to Manobo learners has nine (9) themes that captures the experiences of teachers in handling these Manobo learners. The nine (9) themes are I. Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers, II. Learners' context as characterized by teachers, III. Significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo, IV. Effective teaching strategies, V. Culturally responsive teaching, VI. Resourcefulness in remote teaching, VII. Teachers' motivation in teaching, VIII. Purposeful teaching, and IX. Resilient Teaching.

I. Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram on Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers

In teaching English to Manobo learners, teachers encounter several challenges that deeply influence their experience. These challenges include socioeconomic, geographical, and cultural challenges, along with the reality that teaching often requires more time. By reflecting on their experiences, teachers provide us with a broader understanding of what it is like to teach English in Manobo communities. These everyday realities remind us of that teaching in indigenous communities goes beyond just delivering lessons—it is about making a meaningful connection with learners through empathy and patience.

Subtheme 1. Socioeconomic challenges

One significant challenge in English Language Teaching (ELT) to the Manobo community lies in socioeconomic challenges that affect both learning and teaching outcomes. Many learners come from families where parents have little to no formal education, making it hard for them to support their children's academic needs—especially

in English. Some learners start working at an early age to help provide for their families, which affects their focus, energy, and time for school. Others skip classes because of no allowance, walking long distances without food or school supplies, which adds to their daily burden. These situations weigh heavily on teachers, who not only strive to teach but also carry the emotional challenge of understanding and supporting their students' difficult realities.

P1 shared that teaching English to Manobo is hard due to their socioeconomic status.

kung experiences ang pag-uusapan...ah mahirap .mahirap ma'am mahirap magturo ng ng English language sa mga Manobo especially ah ...sa socio economic ah iisss..their their socio economic (Participant 1, page 1, lines 5-6)

Working at a young age resulting in absences due to farming or absences to earn money for the family are mentioned by P1 and P2.

ah yung child labor andyan din ma'am yung mga kwan nila so andaming factors tapos kung may mga may mga parent din na uhmmm... yon na, walang background, walang foundation...sa bahay. So...what do you expect sa mga ganyan ng mga bata (Participant 1, page 6, lines 233-237).

may mga times na palagi sila mag absent dahil ng mag harvest gud sila maam tapos usahay... sa isa ka bulan kay ka dalawa or lima syempre maam gina consider ko yon (Participant 2, page 2, lines 76-78)

Table 1. Socioeconomic challenges as one of the subthemes on challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teacher

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Clusters
kung experiences ang pag-uusapan...ah mahirap .mahirap ma'am mahirap magturo ng ng English language sa mga Manobo especially ah ...sa socio economic ah iisss..their their socio economic (Participant 1, page 1, lines 5-6)	Teaching English to Manobo is difficult due to their socioeconomic status	a. Learners' socioeconomic condition that led them to:
ah yung child labor andyan din ma'am yung mga kwan nila so andaming factors tapos kung may mga may mga parent din na uhmmm... yon na, walang background, walang foundation...sa bahay. So...what do you expect sa mga ganyan ng mga bata (Participant 1, page 6, lines 233-237).	Child labor and parents' educational background are some of the factors affecting English learning among Manobo learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working at a young age • Absences due to farming or working • Absences due to no allowance • Absences to earn money for the family • Helping in the farm • Malnutrition
may mga times na palagi sila mag absent dahil ng mag harvest gud sila maam tapos usahay... sa isa ka bulan kay ka dalawa or lima syempre maam gina consider ko yon (Participant 2, page 2, lines 76-78)	Teacher shares that these learners are frequently absent because of harvesting	
Ang reasons nila maam minsan sa bahay nila maam pag magpatanim ang mga magulang nila sila minsan yong nag-aalaga ng kanilang nakababatang kapatid sa murang edad nila maam kasi marunong na yan sila mag alaga ng kanilang kapatid (Participant 2, page 3, lines 88-90)	Teacher shared that these students are usually absent because of familial responsibilities like taking care of sibling when parents are in farm	b. Early obligation in the family such as:
wala kasing akong baon maam (Participant 2, page 3, lines 92-93)	Teachers also encounter students who are absent because they have no allowance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking care of younger siblings • Helping their parents in the farm

nagtulong ako sa tatay ko maam nag harvest ng mais (Participant 2, page 3, lines 93-94)

Kailangan mo din ng consideration maam sabihin ng consideration din kasi minsan maam yun nga maraming absences sa kanila yung absences talaga hindi mawala sa kanila maam ba kay yun nga sa murang edad nila ah mayroon na silang responsibilidad sa pamilya nila maam kasi minsan hindi nalang sila mag aral muna ngayon kay dahil may trabaho ang tatay sila muna yung mag aalaga ng kanilang kapatid yun yung alam so dapat iconsider din yung mga kasama kung teacher. (Participant 2, page 6, lines 225-229)

is yung absenteeism kay tungod mag harvest sang kape, mag tabang sa ginikanan (Participant 4, page 9, lines 310-311)

kasi we can't force them to attend school knowing na pumunta sila ng ng ng palayan nila to work, mag-hurnal, mag-linis, to work, and to put food on their table so so the progress is I think gradual... (Participant 5, page 3, lines 86-88)

It's just that their current state in theirs. Personally, ito talaga ang naging problem ko because I can't force my learners to attend school consistently kasi nga they have to work (Participant 5, page 3, lines 112-113)

when you're teaching in English in lower grades ma mahirap talaga siya kasi uhh maturo mo yung few words sa kanila pagdating sa bahay, yung follow up kasi ang kailangan natin doon... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14)

siguro sa malnutrition na rin na mga ano ng mga problema nila ba (Participant 6, page 2, lines 82-83)

different kasi ang level ng understanding ng IP kasi itong mga bata na ito, nagtatrabaho yan noh, tulad ngayon harvest time ng coffee ang attendance ng bata namin doon almost 50% ang wala. (Participant 6, page 6, lines 257-259)

Teacher shared that these learners help their parents in farming
Learners' frequent absences due to familial responsibilities such as taking care of their younger siblings

c. Parents with no educational background

Absenteeism because of helping their parents in farming

Teacher shares how these learners absent in school because many of them must work to help their families

They have to work which leads them to absences

Socioeconomic status of parents that affects learners' learning pace

Malnutrition as a factor affecting their learning pace

These learners have different way of learning and may be absent in class for almost 50% because of harvesting.

P2 also talked about the early obligation of these learners in their family such as taking care of younger siblings when parents go to farm and helping their parents in farming.

Ang reasons nila maam minsan sa bahay nila maam pag magpatanim ang mga magulang nila sila minsan yong nag-aalaga ng kanilang nakababatang kapatid sa murang edad nila maam kasi marunong na yan sila mag alaga ng kanilang kapatid (Participant 2, page 3, lines 88-90)

nagtulong ako sa tatay ko maam nag harvest ng mais (Participant 2, page 3, lines 93-94)

P2 also shared that one of the reasons for their absences is due to no allowance.

wala kasing akong baon maam (Participant 2, page 3, lines 92-93)

These frequent absences contribute to the factors affecting their learning pace. P6 also added that the educational background of their parents and malnutrition are added factors affecting their learning pace.

when you're teaching in English in lower grades ma mahirap talaga siya kasi uhh maturo mo yung few words sa kanila pagdating sa bahay, yung follow up kasi ang kailangan natin doon... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14)

siguro sa malnutrition na rin na mga ano ng mga problema nila ba (Participant 6, page 2, lines 82-83)

On the part of teachers, these socioeconomical challenges faced by the learners are acknowledged and given consideration for this is the reality among these learners.

Kailangan mo din ng consideration maam sabihin ng consideration din kasi minsan maam yun nga maraming absences sa kanila yung absences talaga hindi mawala sa kanila maam ba kay yun nga sa murang edad nila ah mayroon na silang responsibilidad sa pamilya nila maam kasi minsan hindi nalang sila mag aral muna ngayon kay dahil may trabaho ang tatay sila muna yung mag aalaga ng kanilang kapatid yun yung alam so dapat iconsider din yung mga kasama kung teacher. (Participant 2, page 6, lines 225-229)

In a study of Cummins (2007), it is stated that frequent absences disrupt learning, limiting the learners' exposure to English. Additionally, their daily labor affects their energy and concentration in class (UNESCO, 2019). These experiences point out the need for flexible learning programs and community support to accommodate Manobo students' unique socioeconomic realities.

Subtheme 2. Geographical challenges

Geographical challenges greatly affect the teaching-learning process in Manobo communities, where many schools are located in remote and hard-to-reach areas. The lack of electricity resulting to limited access in electronic media and lack of internet access hinders both teaching delivery and student learning. This situation adds to another hurdle that an English teacher to a Manobo community must face.

Table 2. Excerpts on Geographical challenges as one of the subthemes on challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teacher

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
hindi sa pag discriminate but uhm ahhh malayo sa kabihasanan (Participant 1, page 1, line 8) ako dati walang wala lahat eh walang kuryente... hindi ako makapag kwan..kung laptop naman ma'am iyong laptop ko non ganito lang kaliit (Participant 1, page 1, lines 23-24).	These learners are far from the urban community Teacher has limitation in terms of using instructional materials due to lack of electricity.	a. Far school location leading to:
e wala gani cellphone didto walay kuryente didto, oo...yan, yan pa isa pa yang mga factor mga exposure gud nila ma'am saaa kuan sa real world hindi pa masyado....(Participant 1, page 6, lines 237-241).	Teacher shares how limited access and exposure to technology creates gap in the teaching process.	• Lack of electricity resulting to: preparing of IMS back home no use of electronic media
Ang school namo ngaman abi nag kalayu layu nga eskwelehan dire sa Kalamansig... Kung may	Teacher described their school as the farthest in their municipality	• Inadequate infrastructure for

far flung pa sa far flung.... (laugh) (Participant 4, page 2, lines 41, 43)		communication and electricity
Barriers siguro didto sa amon ang accessibility? Kasi wala kami kuryente... tapos...uhm, ang accessibility sa internet...So, behind kaayo kami wala internet, wala kuryente, so daw so remote area ni siya kaayo, so need mo pa diri sa baba. ahh para ang mga needs mo... (Participant 4, page 5, lines 180-182)	Lack of electricity and internet connection so teachers have to prepare their needs back home	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited access and exposure to technology • Lack of internet connection
di himuon mo ni sa baba kay e-ano lang sa taas kay ihatud mo pud didto. So yun one of the... barriers is the distance and the...wala gid kuryente didto abi. (Participant 4, page 5, lines 184-185)	Teachers need to make their teaching materials back home due to lack of electricity	
there's no electricity ahh... walang... pati only means of communications is yung walkie talkie yung icon, yun lang ma'am ahh, electricity kasi I think factor din (Participant 5, page 4, lines 156-158)	Lack of electricity and poor communication	
Manobo community sa *** na without uhh, technology pa, walang kuryente uhh, walang mga television, bibihira lang may radio. (Participant 6, page 1, lines 8-9)	Lack of electricity leading to unavailability of electronic media	

P1 and P4 talked about their school location which is away from the urban area.

hindi sa pag discriminate but uhm ahhh malayo sa kabihasanan (Participant 1, page 1, line 8)

Ang school namo ngaman abi nag kalayu layu nga eskwelehan dire sa Kalamansig... Kung may far flung pa sa far flung.... (laugh) (Participant 4, page 2, lines 41, 43) ako dati walang wala lahat eh walang kuryente... hindi ako makapag kwan..kung laptop naman ma'am iyong laptop ko non ganito lang kaliit (Participant 1, page 1, lines 23-24).

P1, P4, P5, and P6 all mentioned the lack of electricity, which forces them to prepare instructional materials at home and leads to either no use or limited use of electronic media for teaching English.

e wala gani cellphone didto walay kuryente didto, oo....yan, yan pa isa pa yang mga factor mga exposure gud nila ma'am saaa kuan sa real world hindi pa masyado....(Participant 1, page 6, lines 237-241).

di himuon mo ni sa baba kay e-ano lang sa taas kay ihatud mo pud didto. So yun one of the... barriers is the distance and the...wala gid kuryente didto abi. (Participant 4, page 5, lines 184-185)

there's no electricity ahh... walang... pati only means of communications is yung walkie talkie yung icon, yun lang ma'am ahh, electricity kasi I think factor din (Participant 5, page 4, lines 156-158)

*Manobo community sa *** na without uhh, technology pa, walang kuryente uhh, walang mga television, bibihira lang may radio. (Participant 6, page 1, lines 8-9)*

As mentioned in the statement of P6 above, learners also lack exposure to technology in their community. This was agreed upon by P1, who said:

e wala gani cellphone didto walay kuryente didto, oo....yan, yan pa isa pa yang mga factor mga exposure gud nila ma'am saaa kuan sa real world hindi pa masyado....(Participant 1, page 6, lines 237-241).

This points out how students' limited contact with the modern world slows down their understanding of globally relevant content in English. According to Gay (2018), the remote location of school in mountainous regions poses significant challenges to accessing quality education, thereby limiting the educational opportunities available to learners. This situation calls for extra effort on the part of teachers to deliver their lessons effectively.

Subtheme 3. Cultural challenges

The Manobo, as one of the indigenous groups in the Philippines, have a rich cultural heritage that is deeply rooted in their identity. However, one of their cultural practices—early marriage affects the learning of these learners.

Table 3. Excerpts on Cultural challenges as one of the subthemes on challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teacher

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
kasi andami mong kalaban dyan ma'am eh kasi nam number one dyan theeee kwan ang dami dyan ma'am yung culture ang kalaban mo dyan ma'am culture sinasabi ko cultu culture kasi ang dami dyang early marriage (Participant 1, page 6, lines 233-237). So, ilan ito sila dati, 23 out of 23, kasi naging 13 nalang sila ngayon. So ang iba kasi nag-asawa ganon ma'am. (Participant 3, page 5, lines 186-187)	Cultural barrier in ELT to Manobo due to early marriage The teacher also shared that enrollment among Manobo learners has significantly decreased due to early marriage practices	a. Cultural practice: • Early marriage leading to decreased enrollment

As P3 shared several learners are dropping out of school because of early marriages.

So, ilan ito sila dati, 23 out of 23, kasi naging 13 nalang sila ngayon. So ang iba kasi nag-asawa ganon ma'am. (Participant 3, page 5, lines 186-187)

Fortunately, the Manobo community is now more aware of the effects of early marriage. In a study by Ballista and Dioso (2024), Manobo parents in Sto. Niño, Loreto, Agusan del Sur, shared their concerns about early marriage. They stressed the value of education and discouraged early marriage, especially for girls, believing that education can improve their lives. While early marriage still creates challenges for Manobo learners, many are working hard to overcome it with the help of their families and communities.

Subtheme 4. Teaching takes more time than usual

Teachers shared their experiences of having longer teaching hours compared to learners in urban areas, due to the poor retention of learners and the whole process involved in teaching English to Manobo learners.

Table 4. Excerpts on Teaching takes more time than usual as one of the subthemes on challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teacher

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Oo mag magdugay gid siya maam e (Participant 2, page 1, line 25) malimtan nila maam ba asta nga pagbalik tudluan mo naman gid sila (Participant 2, page 2, lines 81-82) you have to process everything, kung mag turo ka ng subject na English matagalan ka, so an hour, an hour period of class kulang. (Participant 3, page 1, lines 13-14) dati one and half ata naga budget ako niyan one and half pero kulang pa din (Participant 3, page 1, lines 18-19)	ELT to Manobo learners takes more time Reteaching of lessons due to low retention level of learners Teaching them takes more time than usual since you have to process everything Allocating sufficient time for ELT to Manobo learners but still find it insufficient Teacher shared how different these learners are compared to urban learners. It takes longer hours of teaching.	a. Teaching takes more time than usual due to: • Allotment of more teaching time than usual • Reteaching due to learners' poor retention • Processing everything • Different learning pace of Manobo learners compared to urban areas
hindi katulad sa mga estudyante doon sa baba kase isang instruction mo lang isang discussion mo lang makuha nila lahat no.. uahh almost makakuha na agad sa discussion mo unlike sa bukid sa bundok... uhmmm minsan ang isang topic one week ko pa matapos (Participant 4, page 1, lines 8-10) so magbalikbalik nagabalikbalik ka lang (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14) isang objective yan minsan it will last a week bago mo ma achieve yan sya so pipiliin mo lang yun yung mga basic na objective ang gagamitin mo para maturo mo sa kanila kasi kung iinsist mo talaga yung that day na objective di gid kamo mag karamual gid wala gid (Participant 6, page 5, lines 223-225)	Teacher shares on the need for reteaching Teaching takes time, so teachers should not insist on unattainable objectives.	b. Teaching takes more time than usual so: • Teachers must make sure to only have attainable teaching objectives

P2 and P6 agreed on doing reteaching because of the learners' poor retention leading to longer hours of teaching.

malimtan nila maam ba asta nga pagbalik tudluan mo naman gid sila (Participant 2, page 2, lines 81-82)

so magbalikbalik nagabalikbalik ka lang (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14)

Moreover, P3 shared that an hour of teaching these Manobo learners is insufficient because you have to process everything as a teacher which also includes stages of translation to transfer information with them which is also intensified by P6 saying that one lesson objective may last for a week to achieve that is why teachers must make sure to only have attainable teaching objectives.

*you have to process everything, kung mag turo ka ng subject na English matagalan ka, so an hour, an hour period of class kulang. (Participant 3, page 1, lines 13-14)
dati one and half ata naga budget ako niyan one and half pero kulang pa din (Participant 3, page 1, lines 18-19)*

isang objective yan minsan it will last a week bago mo ma achieve yan sya so pipiliin mo lang yun yung mga basic na objective ang gagamitin mo para maturo mo sa kanila kasi kung iinsist mo talaga yung that day na objective di gid kamo mag karamual gid wala gid (Participant 6, page 5, lines 223-225)

Additionally, P4 shared how different these learners are in terms of grasping the lessons compared to the learning in urban areas.

hindi katulad sa mga estudyante doon sa baba kase isang instruction mo lang isang discussion mo lang makuha nila lahat no.. uahh almost makakuha na agad sa discussion mo unlike sa bukid sa bundok... uhmmm minsan ang isang topic one week ko pa matapos (Participant 4, page 1, lines 8-10)

These findings align with Burton (2013) which found that indigenous language speakers required additional instructional time to achieve proficiency in English due to linguistic and cultural factors affecting the learning process. This is another challenge that an English teacher to Manobo learners must handle.

II. Learners' context as characterized by the teachers

Figure 4. Schematic Diagram on the Learners' context as characterized by teachers

Learning English can be challenging for many learners due to several factors described by teachers. One key issue is their limited English language exposure, which makes it difficult for them to practice and build fluency. The absence of phonetic sound from L1 causes difficulty in L2, especially in pronunciation. Teachers also observe learners' low retention, meaning they often forget what they have learned. In addition, learners' slow learning pace makes it harder for them to keep up with lessons.

Subtheme 1. Limited English language exposure

Teachers shared that one of the main challenges in teaching English to Manobo learners is their limited exposure to the language. Because they rarely hear or use English in daily life, their basic language skills remain weak. This lack of exposure makes it harder for them to understand lessons and build confidence in using the language.

Table 5. Excerpts on Limited English language exposure as one of the subthemes on learners' context as characterized by teachers

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
umiikot lang kasi sila within their ah... within their community na malayo kung baga (Participant 1, page 1, lines 7-8)	Learners stay within their community	a. Limited English language exposure due to:
... kung baga iyong roots nila when it comes to English language ma'am mababa talaga (Participant 1, page 1, lines 9-10)	Teacher observed these learners having limited background in English	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staying only in their remote community • Limited exposure outside the community
On writing dyan.. din tayo mag dyan na naman another challenges na naman tayo dyan ma'am, another challenge na naman sa writing kasi..... uhmmm pag....pag...words ang pag-uusapan yong per word kayang kaya... pero pag dating na sa formulation ng sentences... simple paragraph nagkaka kwan.... doon nagkaka.....problema doon sa... ano ..kasi daw kwan lang abi maam ba ..ngggggg.... kung baga..... back to kwan ka kasi lahat basic (Participant 1, page 4, lines 135-139).	Writing problem occurs with the Manobo learners due to poor background in English language	b. Limited English language exposure leading to:
hmm oo naman ma'am, kasi yung pag pasok namin that time kahit good morning nga hindi nila masabi ma'am eh... hmmm ... that's that's the first simple ... kumbaga first English na matutunan mo. (Participant 1, page 4, lines 146-147).	Teacher shares that these learners have difficulty with common English expressions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor English background • Slow learning pace compared to learners in urban area learners • Difficulty with basic English words or expressions • Lack of response from the learners • Going back to the basics of English language • Longer hours of teaching • Difficulty in teaching the language • Unfamiliarity of the basic sounds
kasi nahahalata ko ma'am no good morning good morning everyone kasi ganun good mo nakatunganga lang sila sayo ganun pero nong ma.. mafeon mafeon lafos minanobo ko sila go sila mafeon ganun sila sir mafeon pero nong good morning ganun ako tingin lang sila sa akin so it means di wala talaga (Participant 1, page 4, lines 150-153).	Teacher experienced just being stared by learners when speaking in English pointing out their unfamiliarity with the language.	
ma'am inistart ko sa mga basic ahh basic ahh conversation like good morning, what is your name, kay nong kasi kung bagsakan sila ng.. tuloy tuloy na English ma'am mag nganga gid sila tapos "hmm" mag ganun sila ba "hmm s-sir naano ka sir?" (laughing) "bakit ka naga English sir?" eh English nga tayo (Participant 1, page 4, lines 173-176).	Teacher started from the basic English expressions and details, so learners could catch up.	
mga ano sila ah ano nga tawag nito e process pa nila yon kung ano nga word na yon (Participant 3, page 1, lines 19-20)	Learners take time processing information such as English words	

Pero before wala pa so, students di la sila ganon ka ano ba, updated sa sa atin globally, nationally so within their ano lang, within their area lang, doon lang sa kanila nga, community community nila sa village lang nila, so hindi ganon sila pa ka aware (Participant 3, page 2, lines 63-65)

Limited learners' exposure outside their community influencing their learning of English language

hindi nila ma master agad agad ang topic mo kasi English bago sa kanilang pandinig iba sa kanilang pandinig no maliban kung Tagalog okay lang lalo na ngayon ahmm..sa akin English mahirap talaga... (Participant 4, page 1, lines 11-13)

Teaching them is difficult because of learners' unfamiliarity of the language

during my time in hours in lower grade, yun ang challenge na nahihirapan ako noon nung hindi man kasi mapa basa... in English, without teaching them the sound of letters (Participant 6, page 3, lines 113-115)

ELT is hard because you have to teach them the basic sounds even in lower grades

P1 and P3 shared that Manobo learners usually stay only within their community wherein there is either no use or limited use of the target language. The learners' limited exposure outside their community influences their learning of English language

umiikot lang kasi sila within their ah... within their community na malayo kung baga (Participant 1, page 1, lines 7-8)

mga ano sila ah ano nga tawag nito e process pa nila yon kung ano nga word na yon (Participant 3, page 1, lines 19-20)

This situation causes writing problems, requiring a return to the basics of English, which leads to a lack of response from learners due to their unfamiliarity with the language, as evidenced in the following responses from P1.

On writing dyan.. din tayo mag dyan na naman another challenges na naman tayo dyan ma'am, another challenge na naman sa writing kasi..... uhmmm pag.....pag...words ang pag-uusapan yong per word kayang kaya... pero pag dating na sa formulation ng sentences... simple paragraph nagkaka kwan.... doon nagkaka.....problema doon sa... ano ..kasi daw kwan lang abi maam ba ..ngggggg.... kung baga..... back to kwan ka kasi lahat basic (Participant 1, page 4, lines 135-139).

ma'am inistart ko sa mga basic ahh basic ahh conversation like good morning, what is your name, kay nong kasi kung bagsakan sila ng.. tuloy tuloy na English ma'am mag ngangang gid sila tapos "hmm" mag ganun sila ba "hmm s-sir naano ka sir?" (laughing) "bakit ka naga English sir?" ehh English nga tayo (Participant 1, page 4, lines 173-176).

kasi nahahalata ko ma'am no good morning good morning everyone kasi ganun good mo nakatunganga lang sila sayo ganun pero nong ma.. mafeon mafeon lafos minanobo ko sila go sila mafeon ganun sila sir mafeon pero nong good morning ganun ako tingin lang sila sa akin so it means di wala talaga (Participant 1, page 4, lines 150-153).

This has been strengthened in the statement of P4 stating that the learners' unfamiliarity of the language leads to difficulty in teaching.

hindi nila ma master agad agad ang topic mo kasi English bago sa kanilang pandinig iba sa kanilang pandinig no maliban kung Tagalog okay lang lalo na ngayon ahmm..sa akin English mahirap talaga... (Participant 4, page 1, lines 11-13)

These findings support Krashen (1982) theory of Second Language Acquisition, which emphasizes the need for clear and consistent language input. When English is not part of learners' daily lives and support is limited, progress becomes difficult—especially with high affective filters and few chances for meaningful use.

Subtheme 2. Absence of Phonetic Sound in L1 Causing Difficulty in L2

The teaching of English to Manobo students is significantly affected by the absence of phonetic sound between their first language (L1) and English (L2), specifically the lack or substitution of certain phonetic sounds such as /r/ and //.

Table 6. Excerpts on absence of phonetic sound in L1 causing difficulty in L2 as one of the subthemes on challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teacher

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
sa Manobo kasi maam wala silang R... At iyong kwan iyong L nila nagiging R then wala silang R ganoon maam like ahh Sir.. they..... use Sil ahhh good molning sil...good molning ganoon so... (Participant 1, page 1, lines 37-39).	Teacher observes the absence of some phonetic sound in the learners' first language.	a. Absence of phonetic sound from L1 causing difficulty in L2 as evident in:
yung sa R gud maam mabudlayan sila like uhhh mag storya sang may r prayer magiging player parang kumbaga yung mamilipit. (Participant 2, page 4, lines 152-153)	Teacher observed these students having struggles in pronouncing R. It becomes L.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners' struggles in pronouncing R and L • Alteration of some words due to mispronunciation
Mamilipit ang dila nila po maam sa red sa color, red magiging led so mag iba na yung meaning sa ano maam so paulit – paulit kahit paulit -paulit mo yan minsan maam iwan ko magbalik talaga yan maam ba yung R nila magiging L. (Participant 2, page 4, lines 155-157)	Pronunciation problem of learners leading to alteration of word meaning, so teacher keeps on correcting the pronunciation of these learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having longer hours of teaching due to correcting errors • Teachers' constant effort to correct the learners' pronunciation
speaking kasi nila... medyo hirap sila dito especially in the words na mayroong L at saka R hindi wala kasi silang... R, yung Sir nila is "Sil" yan siya, ahh... mag gawa yan kahit na yung parents mag gawa ng	Teacher observed these learners struggling to pronounce words with R and L	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need for correcting pronunciation

excuse letter (Participant 6, page 5, lines 191-193)

may mga passage yan siya, sa sa eighteen ko na bata merong anim na hindi maka pronounce ng L diyan, R talaga yan siya so, matagalan kami yan (Participant 6, page 5, lines 197-199)

baguhin siguro eh alangan naman nga anuhon mo na mag highschool na karon kag mag college te sila lang gyapon mag problema sina amo na gina train namon sila nga correct pronunciation sang mga words to challenge gyapon siya. (Participant 6, page 5, lines 209-212)

Teaching takes time because of correcting errors in pronunciation

Teacher corrects the pronunciation of these learners to avoid further problem in their higher level of education

The responses of participants 1, 2, and 6 clearly highlight this scenario among Manobo learners.

sa Manobo kasi maam wala silang R.... At iyong kwan iyong L nila nagiging R then wala silang R ganoon maam like ah Sir.. they..... use Sil ahhh good molning sil...good molning ganoon so... (Participant 1, page 1, lines 37-39).

yung sa R gud maam mabudlayan sila like uhmm mag storya sang may r prayer magiging player parang kumbaga yung mamilipit. (Participant 2, page 4, lines 152-153)

speaking kasi nila... medyo hirap sila dito especially in the words na mayroong L at saka R hindi wala kasi silang... R, yung Sir nila is "Sil" yan siya, ah... mag gawa yan kahit na yung parents mag gawa ng excuse letter (Participant 6, page 5, lines 191-193)

This situation calls for extended class hours because teachers need to correct learners' pronunciation to prevent further problems at higher levels of education, as evidenced in the responses of P6.

may mga passage yan siya, sa sa eighteen ko na bata merong anim na hindi maka pronounce ng L diyan, R talaga yan siya so, matagalan kami yan (Participant 6, page 5, lines 197-199)

baguhin siguro eh alangan naman nga anuhon mo na mag highschool na karon kag mag college te sila lang gyapon mag problema sina amo na gina train namon sila nga correct pronunciation sang mga words to challenge gyapon siya. (Participant 6, page 5, lines 209-212)

These insights strongly reflect Lado (1957) theory that the more different the L2 is from the L1 in sound system, the more difficult it is for learners to master it. Supporting study of Flege (1995) also confirms that learners find it hard to perceive and produce L2

sounds not present in their L1, which aligns with the consistent articulation challenges observed in the Manobo learners. This calls for a thorough and consistent teaching approach with these learners to correct or make them familiar with these letter sounds.

Subtheme 3. Learners' Slow Learning Pace

Teachers often observe that Manobo learners learn at a slower pace compared to learners in urban areas, and they see this as an important part of the learners' context. This slow progress is not simply a matter of ability, it can be influenced by learners' background knowledge and environment.

Table 7. Excerpts on Learner's slow learning pace as one of the subthemes on learners' context as characterized by teachers

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
yung interval ng time ng progress nila is masyadong mahina parin. Mahirap siya kung progress ang babasehan ko well, unlike sa patag na they can do this and that (Participant 5, page 2, lines 80-81)	Teacher's experience on learner's slow learning pace compared to urban learners	a. Learners' slow learning pace:
sa bundok kasi mahirap masasabi ko mahina pero lumalaban yung yung bata.. (Participant 5, page 2, lines 84-85)	The teacher observed that while learners in the mountains may progress slowly, they show determination.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •As compared to learners in urban areas •Yet they are also determined to learn •Liken to late bloomers
parang mga late bloomer kasi yong ..ano.. development ng mga bata (Participant 6, page 2, line 81)	Teacher also observed that these learners seem to be late bloomers	

P5 shared how these learners differ from those in urban areas in terms of learning pace, yet despite this, they remain determined to learn the language, as he further explained.

yung interval ng time ng progress nila is masyadong mahina parin. Mahirap siya kung progress ang babasehan ko well, unlike sa patag na they can do this and that (Participant 5, page 2, lines 80-81)

sa bundok kasi mahirap masasabi ko mahina pero lumalaban yung yung bata.. (Participant 5, page 2, lines 84-85)

Moreover, P6 likened Manobo learners to late bloomers when it comes to English language learning.

parang mga late bloomer kasi yong ..ano.. development ng mga bata (Participant 6, page 2, line 81)

As Vygotsky (1978) explains, learning happens best when students are supported within their zone of proximal development, that is, when tasks are just beyond their current ability but made manageable with the right guidance. From the teachers' perspective, recognizing a slow learning pace is not about labeling students, but about understanding where they are and what kind of help they need to keep growing.

Subtheme 4. Learners' Low Retention

Another concern often raised by teachers is that some students struggle to retain what they have learned over time resulting to reteaching lessons.

Table 8. Excerpts on Learner's low retention as one of the subthemes on learners' context as characterized by teachers

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
kaya minsan kasi sa kadami ng absent absent nila maam ng malimtan gud nila ang ginapabasa maam (Participant 2, page 2, lines 80-81)	Learners' frequent absences result to low retention in English learning	a. Learners' low retention due to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent absences
kasi yung retention nong mga bata, uhh the next day when they return, yung mga words na tinuro mo is wala na... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14)	Teacher shares on learners' low retention level	b. Learners' low retention resulting to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reteaching • Being compared to clean slate
ang problema lang kasi dyan sa... community pagdating lagi sa bahay pagbalik nila especially yong may seminars ka... for 1-week pagbalik mo wala naman parang tabularasa naman yong bata so balik ka na naman (Participant 6, page 2, lines 78-81)	Teacher often reteaches his lessons because these learners have poor retention, they are like clean slate.	

From the teachers' perspective, this low retention becomes evident when learners cannot recall previous lessons, even after repeated instruction which is also caused by their frequent absence as expressed by P2 and P6.

kaya minsan kasi sa kadami ng absent absent nila maam ng malimtan gud nila ang ginapabasa maam (Participant 2, page 2, lines 80-81)

kasi yung retention nong mga bata, uhh the next day when they return, yung mga words na tinuro mo is wala na... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 11-14)

P6 even likened these learners to a clean slate who are starting from scratch with little or no prior exposure to English.

ang problema lang kasi dyan sa... community pagdating lagi sa bahay pagbalik nila especially yong may seminars ka... for 1-week pagbalik mo wala naman parang tabularasa naman yong bata so balik ka na naman (Participant 6, page 2, lines 78-81)

According to Lumontod and Pradia (2023), Manobo learners often find it hard to remember English lessons, especially when dealing with unfamiliar words or when lessons are not connected to their lived experiences. Teachers noted that these learners frequently forgot previous topics, requiring frequent reviews and additional support. This pattern of low retention signals a need for teaching approaches that align more closely with learners' linguistic backgrounds and cultural realities, so that learning becomes more meaningful and lasting.

III. Significant Encounters of Teachers in the Journey of ELT to Manobo

Figure 5. Schematic Diagram on Significant Encounters of Teachers in the Journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo learners highlight various meaningful experiences and insights gathered throughout their teaching practice. These include challenging encounters of teachers, opposing views of ELT to Manobo, and positive attitude of the Manobo tribe. Teachers also experienced positive attitude of Manobo learners in learning English, two-way language exchange between teachers and Manobo learners, and positive experiences of teacher in ELT to Manobo. These encounters shaped their approach, understanding, and connection with the learners and the community.

Subtheme 1. Challenging Encounters of Teachers

Teachers often find themselves in difficult situations when introducing English to Manobo learners, especially when learners show discomfort or hesitation toward the language. In some cases, the teaching process can feel one-sided, with minimal response or participation from learners, making the experience challenging and, at times, discouraging.

Table 9. Excerpts on challenging encounters of teachers as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
they feel hesitant... they feel uncomfortable sa ...pag ang topic na is about English language or sa Science man mapa Science man mapa Math man yan basta mayroong medium.. (Participant 1, page 1, lines 13-15).	Teacher encounters learners who are uncomfortable with the use of English language	a. Challenging encounters of teachers
ang medium of instruction niyo is English talagang ah gumaganon nalang “ <i>sir bat ka nag iEnglish</i> ” may ganun talaga so mahirap yung experience na ganun na (Participant 1, page 1, lines 17-18).	Teacher encounters learners complaining about the use of English language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncomfortable or complaining learners with the use of English language • Frustrating and worse scenarios in ELT
.... Eh kasi ahhh nakaka kwan din eh nakaka kasi di mo gud maturo yung gusto mong ituro ma'am na nakaka kwan din ba naka frustrate yung frustration... (Participant 1, page 6, lines 207-208).	Teacher shares that ELT to Manobo is frustrating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reserve nature of Manobo learners
expect the worst scenario talaga pagdating sa sa teaching lalong lalo na sa mga ma assign ka sa mga far flung areas IPs IP learners (Participant 1, page 6, lines 230-231).	You have to expect the worst scenario when teaching English to IP learners in far flung areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even struggle in Filipino language
mahiyain abi sila ma'am. (Participant 4, page 5, lines 184-185)	The teacher noted challenges due to the	

	learners' reserved nature.
So even though in Filipino language medyo hirap yung mga tribo na makapagsalita ng Filipino language how much more in terms of English (Participant 6, page 1, lines 9-11)	Teacher observes how they struggle even in Filipino language much more with English language.

P1 and P4 shared their experiences with Manobo learners who appeared uncomfortable, reserved, and occasionally expressed complaints about learning the English language. These behaviors posed challenges for the teachers, as they had to find effective strategies to actively engage the learners in the educational process.

they feel hesitant... they feel uncomfortable sa ...pag ang topic na is about English language or sa Science man mapa Science man mapa Math man yan basta mayroong medium... (Participant 1, page 1, lines 13-15).

ang medium of instruction niyo is English talagang ah gumaganon nalang "sir bat ka nag iEnglish" may ganun talaga so mahirap yung experience na ganun na (Participant 1, page 1, lines 17-18).

mahiyain abi sila ma'am. (Participant 4, page 5, lines 184-185)

These encounters led to teachers' frustration, compounded by the fact that they could not teach what they wanted to for these learners, as expressed by P1.

.... Eh kasi ahhh nakaka kwan din eh nakaka kasi di mo gud maturo yung gusto mong ituro ma'am na nakaka kwan din ba naka frustrate yung frustration... (Participant 1, page 6, lines 207-208).

Moreover, P6 also added that these learners are even struggling in Filipino language which increases the language gap between teachers and learners.

So even though in Filipino language medyo hirap yung mga tribo na makapagsalita ng Filipino language how much more in terms of English (Participant 6, page 1, lines 9-11)

According to Liyanage and Walker (2017), these difficulties often come from differences between common English teaching practices and the cultural values of indigenous learners like the Manobo. Their study highlights the need for teachers to understand and respect the local culture when teaching English. They explain that these challenges, while difficult, can help teachers grow professionally by encouraging them to create more respectful and culturally sensitive ways of teaching. In this way, the challenges become a part of the learning process for both teachers and students.

Subtheme 2. Positive attitude of Manobo learners

One significant encounter highlighted by teachers in their ELT journey with Manobo learners is the learners' positive attitude toward learning. Despite challenges, the learners showed enthusiasm in their English class, which creates a more welcoming learning environment.

Table 10. Excerpts on positive attitude of Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Happy sila kasi during your subject ahh meron silang natutunan, may words silang natutunan (Participant 3, page 1, lines 37-39)	Teacher observed that these learners are eager to learn the English language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eager to learn the language • Positive response or behavior in English language learning • Eager to learn since it' is new to them • Remind teachers of their class schedule
positive yong pinapakita nilang attitude kasi nga everytime na makita ka nila they are so happy they're they delighted ahh (Participant 3, page 5, lines 196-197)	Teacher observed that Manobo learners positively respond in ELT	
pag Grade 4,5,6 jan mo na sila makikita yung eagerness nila to learn especially in english hmm ang interesado na gid sila nga you will see some of them pupunta yan sa mga mini library kukuha na yan ng books babasa yan sya (Participant 6, page 2, lines 88-90)	Teacher sees positive learning behavior among these learners as they age	
itong Dulangan Manobo is really eager to learn the English kasi English language kasi kung sa ano pa foreign bago ito sa kanila so interesado ito sila na.. matutunan itong English (Participant 6, page 4, lines 173-175)	Teacher finds these Manobo learners eager to learn English language because its new to them.	
sir mag English na tayo sir, so doon tingnan mo yung oras, o-ay, English na pala. Ohhh, so dun mo makikita na eager sila matuto sa English. (Participant 6, page 5, lines 187-188)	They remind you of your English class schedule showing their eagerness in learning the language	

P3 and P6 expressed that one of the reasons for these learners' eagerness in learning English language is that it is new to them.

positive yong pinapakita nilang attitude kasi nga everytime na makita ka nila they are so happy they're they delighted ahh (Participant 3, page 5, lines 196-197)

itong Dulangan Manobo is really eager to learn the English kasi English language kasi kung sa ano pa foreign bago ito sa kanila so interesado ito sila na.. matutunan itong English (Participant 6, page 4, lines 173-175)

P6 also noted that the learners' eagerness to learn was evident in their actions, such as voluntarily going to the library and reminding their teacher about their English class schedule.

pag Grade 4,5,6 jan mo na sila makikita yung eagerness nila to learn especially in english hmm ang interesado na gid sila nga you will see some of them pupunta yan sa mga mini library kukuha na yan ng books babasa yan sya (Participant 6, page 2, lines 88-90)

sir mag English na tayo sir, so doon tingnan mo yung oras, o-ay, English na pala. Ohhh, so dun mo makikita na eager sila matuto sa English. (Participant 6, page 5, lines 187-188)

This observation aligns with the study of Lumontod and Pradia (2023), who emphasized that indigenous learners, when engaged with cultural sensitivity, tend to respond with enthusiasm and a strong desire to learn. Hence, it is essential for teachers to nurture and sustain these positive attitudes among Manobo learners to create more meaningful and empowering learning experiences.

Subtheme 3. Two-way Language Exchange Between Teachers and Manobo Learners

Another important experience shared by teachers in teaching English to Manobo learners is the two-way language exchange that happens in the classroom. While teachers help learners learn English, they also learn some words and expressions in the Manobo language.

Table 11. Excerpts on Two-way language exchange between teachers and Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
learning for us ako yun talaga ang lalo na kay mga estudyante ko Manobo Dulangan so everyday naga learn ako so parang word by word per day may matutunan talaga ako doon (Participant 3, page 4, lines 139-141)	Teacher is also learning the Manobo language while teaching English with the learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Manobo language while teaching English with them • Becoming familiar with the Manobo language • Learning Manobo language as they teach
Yes po like sa tradition nila uhm didto ko nalalaman... ang word na antang-antang mhm ano gani maam daw kung sa aton mhm kung sa atin mmm mamalayi. (Participant 4, page 3, lines 107-108)	Teachers become familiar of Manobo language	

two-way gyapon, learning gyapon sa amon (Participant 4, page 7, line 232)	Teachers also learn the learner's language while teaching them.
As hindi ka naman Manobo, you are not familiar with their language. A two-way process siya, because you are teaching at the same time you are learning their language din (Participant 6, page 1, lines 21-23)	You are teaching and at the same time learning language which makes ELT to Manobo a two-way process

P3, P4, and P6 shared how their exposure to the Manobo learners gradually led them to become familiar with the Manobo language. Through daily interactions, they began to pick up common phrases, greetings, and cultural expressions, which helped them communicate better and connect more deeply with their students.

As hindi ka naman Manobo, you are not familiar with their language. A two-way process siya, because you are teaching at the same time you are learning their language din (Participant 6, page 1, lines 21-23)

This kind of language exchange is an important part of culturally responsive teaching. When teachers try to learn their students' language, it helps create a more respectful and welcoming classroom. Gay (2018) explains that culturally responsive teaching means understanding and valuing students' cultural backgrounds to help them learn better. In the case of Manobo learners, this two-way exchange allows both teachers and students to grow by learning from each other. It not only improves language skills but also builds trust, respect, and stronger connections in the classroom.

Subtheme 4. Positive experiences of teachers

P4 and P3 shared on their positive encounters with these learners in terms of their learning pace.

Table 12. Excerpts on Positive experiences of teachers as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
may major changes siya.. sa proficiency sa English kasi syempre na notice mo siya like for example pagawain mo siya ng...pssk yong simple explanation lang in a certain topic before one sentence lang tapos as time goes by naging grade 10 na ah 7, 8, 9,10 gradually nagiging proficient siya yong dating one sentence lang yong masasabingayon whole page na siya back to back kakaya na siya no.. so pero hindi naman lahat kasi may mga bata talaga na syempre may may slow learner fast I am referring to	Teacher shared how these learners grow from making simple sentences to rich paragraphs in English over time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners' improvement in English learning • Learners becoming particular with their writings and grammar

fast learner lang na bata (Participant 3, page 4, lines 170-175)

mag essay so makita mo
improvements sa constructing
sentence nila kasi ma ma ano na sila
metikuloso nag gyapon sila sa mga
uhm basic verbs lang mga be verb noh
ahm am is are noh (Participant 4, page 3, lines 94-96)

Observed that learners become meticulous in writing and even correct their own sentences

P3 shared that these learners could possibly improve in writing and P4 added that Manobo learners have become meticulous in writing as time goes on and with the guidance of teachers. While Manobo learners face challenges in English language acquisition, studies indicate that with appropriate support, they can make meaningful progress. Lumontod and Pradia (2023) observed that despite initial difficulties, Manobo students employ various strategies—such as using dictionaries, collaborating with peers, and seeking assistance from teachers—to enhance their English proficiency.

Subtheme 5. Positive attitude of the Manobo tribe

Teachers shared several meaningful encounters that reflect the inherently positive and respectful nature of the Manobo tribe. These encounters were marked by gestures of appreciation, emotional connection, and sincere gratitude from both learners and their families.

Table 13. Excerpts on positive attitude of the Manobo tribe as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Appreciative sila. Open talaga yun sila mag-appreciate talaga yun sila, ma'am. Tapos naga-sulat pa yan sila ng letter, makita mo sa mga notebook kasi always ako nag-check ng notebook. Makita mo doon may mga parang love letter (Participant 3, page 8, lines 313-315)	Learners show appreciation to teachers by writing letters	a. Significant encounters of teachers in the positive nature of Manobo tribe due to:
ano...yung...yung everytime na, kasi doon sa Manobo community, pag once na teacher ma'am, a teacher yan doon a..ano sila parang ikaw yung pinaka espesyal na tao para sa kanila (Participant 4, page 7, lines 245-247)	You become the most special person once you are a teacher in a Manobo community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appreciative nature of Manobo learners • Being treated special • Genuineness of the Manobos • Learners and parents giving recognition and being thankful to them
maka amaze lang sa pakiramdam nga may mga tao na genuine kaayo... (Participant 4, page 7, lines 250)	Teacher is amazed by the genuineness of the Manobos	b. Significant encounters of teachers in the positive nature of Manobo tribe leading to:
I have known the Manobo super grateful talaga being assigned... sa school nayun is I think ...hindi siya naging problem sa akin... instead naging thankful ako (Participant 5, page 2, lines 65-66)	Teacher expresses gratitude being assigned in a school with Manobo learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher's gratitude towards theme
matotouch ka rin somehow, emotionally ganun... (Participant 5, page 2, line 76)	Teacher also shares how these learners affect him emotionally	

<p>marereceive ka na ganon na recognition sa mga bata especially lalo na mga parents lalo na pag mag general assembly sasabihin sayo na magpasalamat ka kay sir na ganito kasi napabasa niya yong anak napabasa yong anak niya so nakakataba rin ng puso (Participant 6, page 4, lines 142-144)</p>	<p>Teachers receive recognition from learners and parents saying how thankful they are for teaching them read.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A reason of teacher to be emotionally affected
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For instance, Participant 3 shared that Manobo learners express their appreciation through heartfelt gestures such as writing letters, often found in their notebooks, even resembling affectionate notes.

Appreciative sila. Open talaga yun sila mag-appreciate talaga yun sila, ma'am. Tapos naga-sulat pa yan sila ng letter, makita mo sa mga notebook kasi always ako nag-check ng notebook. Makita mo doon may mga parang love letter (Participant 3, page 8, lines 313–315)

Similarly, P4 stated, that you are treated as special in a Manobo community and even added that he was amazed by their genuineness.

ano...yung...yung everytime na, kasi doon sa Manobo community, pag once na teacher ma'am, a teacher yan doon a..ano sila parang ikaw yung pinaka espesyal na tao para sa kanila (Participant 4, page 7, lines 245-247)

maka amaze lang sa pakiramdam nga may mga tao na genuine kaayo... (Participant 4, page 7, lines 250)

These positive nature of Manobo learners and parents led teachers to become grateful and emotionally attached with these people in the Manobo community.

I have known the Manobo super grateful talaga being assigned... sa school nayun is I think ...hindi siya naging problem sa akin... instead naging thankful ako (Participant 5, page 2, lines 65-66)

matotouch ka rin somehow, emotionally ganun... (Participant 5, page 2, line 76)

marereceive ka na ganon na recognition sa mga bata especially lalo na mga parents lalo na pag mag general assembly sasabihin sayo na magpasalamat ka kay sir na ganito kasi napabasa niya yong anak napabasa yong anak niya so nakakataba rin ng puso (Participant 6, page 4, lines 142-144)

These findings are supported by the work of Gay (2010), who argued that culturally responsive teaching involves not just curriculum relevance but genuine relationship-building with students and communities. She emphasized that valuing learners' cultural expressions and emotional warmth enhances both motivation and meaningful learning. The Manobo learners' expressions of appreciation and respect mirror this principle,

confirming that emotional and cultural reciprocity between teachers and indigenous communities can strengthen educational engagement and teacher satisfaction.

Subtheme 6. Opposing views of ELT to Manobo learners

Teachers shared that they encounter differing perspectives not only among learners but also within themselves.

Table 14. Excerpts on Opposing views of ELT to Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on significant encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Fun masaya man din sa kwan masaya man din sila kaya lang, andun yung sabi ko kanina na parang hesitant sila... kumbaga takot uhmm (Participant 1, page 4, lines 158-160).	Teacher shared that these learners are also enjoying in English language learning, but their anxiety is also there.	a. Opposing view of learners: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learners enjoy but are also anxious
kung may negative man na mahirap ganito frustration pero..masaya din kasi... kasi kwan ma'am yung kumbaga ma motivate ka din sa kanila ma'am na magturo kasi kumbaga yung gaya ng good morning lang gani noon good morning noon hindi nga nila ma appreciate yung good morning kasi or hindi man nila maintindihan yung good morning ngayon ah sila pa mismo mag good morning ganun yung sila sila na rin mismo nag cocorrect sa kanila (Participant 1, page 6, lines 211-215).	Even if there is frustration in teaching, you will still be motivated when you see these learners improving and even correcting themselves.	b. Opposing views of teachers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ELT to Manobo is both frustrating and motivation Difficult yet enjoyable Fun yet difficult
mahirap.. as at the same time enjoy kasi..ng nakikita mo sa sa mga mukha ng estudyante mo na kung ano ang English ng ganitong bagay ma amaze sila sa ah ganito pala ang English ng ganito pala ang English ng dahon sir (Participant 4, page 1, lines 5-7)	Difficult yet enjoyable when you see your learners' reaction as they learn new words	
masaya sya na mahirap (Participant 6, page 1, line 23)	Fun yet difficult	

P1 expressed that these learners are enjoying but at the same time anxious in English language.

Fun masaya man din sa kwan masaya man din sila kaya lang, andun yung sabi ko kanina na parang hesitant sila... kumbaga takot uhmm (Participant 1, page 4, lines 158-160).

P1, P4, and P6 also shared their opposing views in ELT to Manobo saying that it is both enjoyable and difficult. This is caused by their struggles in delivering instruction with these learners, yet teachers found happiness in their learner's progress and enthusiasm for learning English language.

mahirap.. as at the same time enjoy kasi..ng nakikita mo sa sa mga mukha ng estudyante mo na kung ano ang English ng ganitong bagay ma amaze sila sa ah ganito pala ang English ng ganito pala ang English ng dahon sir (Participant 4, page 1, lines 5-7)

masaya sya na mahirap (Participant 6, page 1, line 23)

Burton (2013) highlights that teaching English to Manobo learners is difficult due to cultural and language gaps, yet many teachers still find it enjoyable as they witness students' progress. This shows that ELT to Manobo can be both challenging and fulfilling.

IV. Effective Teaching Strategies for Manobo Learners

Figure 6. Schematic Diagram on Effective Teaching Strategies for Manobo Learners

In teaching English to Manobo learners, the use of clear and effective strategies plays a vital role in supporting their learning progress. While consistency in teaching concepts, the use of rewards, engaging activities, and cooperative learning are common classroom practices, it is important to note that these approaches have proven especially effective for Manobo learners due to their specific learning needs and educational context.

Subtheme 1. Consistency in Teaching a Concept

This emphasizes the importance of repetition in teaching Manobo learners, as a consistent approach helps reinforce their understanding.

Table 15. Excerpts on Consistency in teaching a concept as one of the subthemes on effective teaching strategies to Manobo learners

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
yon na iyong parang daily routine namin, na kada mag start kami ng klase yon yong una naming ginagawa na kwan para para lang para lang ma kwan iyong dila nila maam exercise tongue exercise nila maam yong mga ganoon... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 49-51).	Teacher does daily tongue exercises to improve the learner's pronunciation	Consistency in teaching a concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily tongue exercise to improve pronunciation • Repeating of lessons • Constant use of flashcards • Consistency in teaching English
routine na namin na yon lang before we start okay let's read first our ganito prepared rhyme or mother ahh tongue tongue ... exercise yon lang tapos everyday yon or at least thrice a week ganoon ...na ginagawa namin then later on na memorize na... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 54-56).	Teacher makes tongue exercises as a part of daily routine to promote memorization	
more on repetition para ma assess di ko ma assess sa una-una dayon... ang repetition tatlo ka adlaw. (Participant 4, page 3, lines 89-90)	Repetition of lessons to make them learned	
Flashcards... every morning kapag papasok sila sa- sa- sa- sa classroom, parang ginawa ko siyang practice na umm it's not- it's not na hindi sila makapasok sa school but they have to read that word before entering my classroom (Participant 5, page 2, lines 49-53)	Constant use of flashcards to foster learning among learners	
Ano lang constant reading lang siya... ahhh... wag mo talagang...halimbawa ahhh... consistency yun siya.. be consistent in teaching English, wag mong... wag mo siyang laktaw laktawan na ngayong halimbawa nagturo ka ng English, bukas parang makalimutan mo	Be consistent in teaching the language	

siya, kung pwede araw-araw mo
(Participant 6, page 6, lines 244-247)

P1 shared how he was able to make his learners memorize a poem by doing daily tongue exercises.

routine na namin na yon lang before we start okay let's read first our ganito prepared rhyme or mother ahh tongue tongue ... exercise yon lang tapos everyday yon or at least thrice a week ganoon ...na ginagawa namin then later on na memorize na... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 54-56).

P4 talked about repeating of lessons before assessing the learning of these learners given the fact that most Manobo learners have poor retention level and slow learning pace.

more on repetition para ma assess di ko ma assess sa una-una dayon... ang repetition tatlo ka adlaw. (Participant 4, page 3, lines 89-90)

That has been intensified by P6 stating that teachers must teach the subject on daily basis especially in their multigrade teaching set up.

Ano lang constant reading lang siya... ahhh... wag mo talagang...halimbawa ahhh... consistency yun siya.. be consistent in teaching English, wag mong... wag mo siyang laktaw laktawan na ngayong halimbawa nagturo ka ng English, bukas parang makalimutan mo siya, kung pwede araw-araw mo (Participant 6, page 6, lines 244-247)

According to Tomlinson (2011), consistent and well-structured instruction is essential in language teaching as it provides learners with clear expectations and supports gradual skill development. Regular exposure to language patterns and repeated practice allows students to internalize concepts more effectively. This approach is particularly helpful for Manobo learners who need more time and reinforcement to grasp new content.

Subtheme 2. Use of Rewards

This one focuses on how positive reinforcement can motivate learners to participate and perform better in language learning which is also effective among Manobo learners.

P3 shared on how she used rewards such candies and additional points to motivate students in doing learning tasks such as spelling.

nag spelling kasi yun mahirapan sila sa spelling so, ahh enjoyable sila yan yung kumpara para parang parang (stuttering) ano ba? Ano ba tawag ito yung? Yung,

yung moment na mga bata nag-eeenjoy kasi they know na may ibibigay akong (Participant 3, page 1, lines 28-31)

Table 16. Excerpts on Use of rewards as one of the subthemes on effective teaching strategies to Manobo learners

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
nag spelling kasi yun mahirapan sila sa spelling so, ahh enjoyable sila yan yung kumpara para parang parang (stuttering) ano ba? Ano ba tawag ito yung? Yung, yung moment na mga bata nag-eeenjoy kasi they know na may ibibigay akong (Participant 3, page 1, lines 28-31)	Rewards motivate them from doing difficult tasks like spelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivate the learners in doing tasks such spelling • Motivate them in learning • Excite theme • Make reviewing of lessons more engaging
halimbawa ano may candy akong dala tapos yung nanalo syempre may plus 5 na may candy pa, so they are, they were going to be motivated to join to everytime na makita nila ako, ay yan mag spelling so, para sa akin ahh atleast ahh pagkakita nila sayo motivated sila to learn the language so (Participant 3, page 1, lines 34-37)	Teacher gives candies and additional points as rewards to motivate learners in learning the language	
Reward theory of, reward when, yung conditioning nga pagmakita ka nila ganon... (Participant 3, page 1, lines 37-39)	Learners get excited seeing their teachers who give them reward	
review ko ng mga may mga list ako sang English words nga gina .gigiha ha..ginahambal ko ni sa ila previous topics ana so before na mag start ang klase... may ano na to oh sino ang maka...bigay ng English nag ani to may singko..so parang ..(laughing)...gina serve ko nalang na motivation para mas ma ma mag take note na sila sa mga word (Participant 4, page 7-8, lines 262-265)	Reviewing of lessons made more engaging by giving of reward	

P3 shared on how she used rewards such candies and additional points to motivate students in doing learning tasks such as spelling.

nag spelling kasi yun mahirapan sila sa spelling so, ahh enjoyable sila yan yung kumpara para parang parang (stuttering) ano ba? Ano ba tawag ito yung? Yung,

yung moment na mga bata nag-eejoy kasi they know na may ibibigay akong (Participant 3, page 1, lines 28-31)

The anticipation of a small prize turns a difficult activity into something enjoyable. Another teacher described how turning lessons into friendly competitions, with candies and bonus points as rewards, boosts participation:

halimbawa ano may candy akong dala tapos yung nanalo syempre may plus 5 na may candy pa, so they are, they were going to be motivated to join to everytime na makita nila ako, ay yan mag spelling so, para sa akin ahh atleast ahh pagkakita nila sayo motivated sila to learn the language so (Participant 3, page 1, lines 34-37)

Reviewing has also been made easier when the teacher uses rewards as expressed by P4.

review ko ng mga may mga list ako sang English words nga gina .gigiha ha..ginahambal ko ni sa ila previous topics ana so before na mag start ang klase... may ano na to oh sino ang maka...bigay ng English nag ani to may singko..so parang ..(laughing)...gina serve ko nalang na motivation para mas ma ma mag take note na sila sa mga word (Participant 4, page 7-8, lines 262-265)

A related study by Tolero and Echaure (2021) examined the relationship between learning motivation, rewards, and academic achievement among junior high school students in the Botolan District, Zambales. The study found that both tangible and intangible rewards positively influenced students' motivation, leading to improved academic performance. This underscores the effectiveness of reward systems in enhancing learner engagement and success, particularly in resource-constrained educational settings.

Subtheme 3. Use of engaging teaching activities

This one highlights the importance of capturing learners' attention through interactive and enjoyable classroom experiences and promoting learners' class engagement by allowing them to speak in their language.

Table 17. Excerpts on Use of engaging teaching activities as one of the subthemes on effective teaching strategies to Manobo learners

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
sa aking grade 10 stu grade 10 mga learners di ng ano Manobo Dulangan ginagawa ko naman sa kanila is ahh, may mga celebrity gina ask ko yan sila kung anong celebrity halimbawa, kung may kilala sila. What if, ikaw yung celebrity na celebrity na yun? (Participant 3, page 1, lines 40-42)	Use of exciting learning activities to encourage learners' participation.	a. Use of engaging teaching activities such as:
alam naman natin yung charades din talaga kung papaano siya ginagawa... eh ang ginagawa nila (clearing throat) nag- maliban sa nag-eejoy sila, nagleleaarn na rin sila. (Participant 5, page 1, lines 29-30)	Game-based learning allows them to enjoy while learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exciting learning activities • Game-based learning a. Use of engaging teaching activities to:

spelling muna... as my practice na rin sa kanila in in teaching teaching English so so magbibigay ako ng word and then they have to spell that for them to enter my my classroom (Participant 5, page 2, lines 54-56)

Teacher uses exciting strategies to promote spelling among these learners

- Promote learners' engagement in learning tasks

P3 and P5 shared on how an exciting activity could encourage participation of learners saying:

sa aking grade 10 stu grade 10 mga learners di ng ano Manobo Dulangan ginagawa ko naman sa kanila is ahh, may mga celebrity gina ask ko yan sila kung anong celebrity halimbawa, kung may kilala sila. What if, ikaw yung celebrity na celebrity na yun? (Participant 3, page 1, lines 40-42)

alam naman natin yung charades din talaga kung papaano siya ginagawa... eh ang ginagawa nila (clearing throat) nag- maliban sa nag-eejoy sila, naglelearn na rin sila. (Participant 5, page 1, lines 29-30)

This shows that incorporating games in the teaching process will make your learners happy while learning. The use of engaging teaching activities, such as local games, role-playing, and interactive storytelling, has been shown to foster active learning and improve literacy development among Manobo learners by making lessons more relevant and enjoyable. According to Saysi et al. (2022), incorporating exciting activities like community-based language games and culturally rooted classroom environment can address pedagogical gaps and motivate indigenous students, ultimately contributing to more effective and inclusive language instruction.

Subtheme 4. Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning, as an effective teaching strategy, plays a vital role in enhancing the academic engagement of Manobo learners by promoting peer interaction, shared responsibility, and collaborative problem-solving.

Table 18. Excerpts on Cooperative learning as one of the subthemes on effective teaching strategies to Manobo learners

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
nagtutulungan tulungan naman sila like say for example sa mga group works group activites (Participant 3, page 6, lines 234-235)	Teacher also observed cooperation among these learners in group activities	Cooperative learning for:
palagi kong ini-integrate talaga yung group activities kasi I feel like mas nagle-learn sila doon uhm especially sa performance task noh? (Participant 5, page 1, lines 17-18)	Use of group activities to promote learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation in group activities • Promoting learning in group activities

P3 and P5 promoted cooperation among Manobo learners using cooperative learning strategies, particularly group activities. These activities encouraged

teamwork, mutual support, and peer-to-peer interaction, which are key cultural values of the Manobo.

In conclusion, cooperative learning strategies, like group activities, enhance collaboration and engagement among Manobo learners. Aligning teaching with their cultural values supports a dynamic learning environment and improves academic performance. Lumontod and Pradia (2023) note that cooperative learning significantly boosts language acquisition and student engagement among Manobo learners.

V. Culturally Responsive Teaching

Figure 7. Schematic Diagram on Culturally Responsive Teaching

Culturally responsive teaching is important in English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners. ELT to Manobo requires translation to help students understand better in their native language. It also needs cultural consideration to respect their way of life and traditions. Lastly, learner-based teaching helps meet the specific needs and learning styles of Manobo students.

Subtheme 1. ELT to Manobo requires Translation

In this study, the use of translation emerged as an important element of culturally responsive teaching. Since English is not the first language of Manobo learners, teachers often rely on translating instructions or concepts into the learners' mother tongue to ensure understanding. This strategy helps bridge language gaps, reduces confusion, and makes learning more accessible and respectful of the learners' linguistic background.

Table 19. Excerpts on ELT to Manobo requires translation as one of the subthemes on culturally responsive teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
<p>you try to use other language minsan ahh yung mother tongue nila mismo tinatranslate pa namin ma'am yung ang kahirap (Participant 1, page 1, lines 19-20).</p> <p>so ang hirap ng teaching ng kuan ng experience ko sa pagteach ng English ma'am kasi you need to translate in their mother tongue (Participant 1, page 1, lines 27-28).</p> <p>itranslate into Manobo dialect yong mga lesson ko ma'am.... sa kanila... (Participant 2, page 1, lines 7)</p> <p>Gaparticipate man sila maam pag na translate mo kinausap mo sila or like magtanong sila sa English sa Manobo yan magparticipate. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 176-177)</p> <p>you have to have some translation, major major translation may from English word and then itranslate mo siya sa Filipino afterwards itranslate mo pa yun siya ng Ilonggo and kung hindi pa rin makuha ng bata you ask them to translate it kung may idea sila what what is that word in their vernacular sa Manobo na language (Participant 3, page 1, lines 5-8)</p> <p>then afterwards let's help on that na gawin siyang English ang translation niya is ito ito so you can ano yan so ang nagyayari maam everytime na naga pagawa ako ng essay maam ano ang English ng ano maam? (Participant 3, pages 5, lines 215-217)</p> <p>matudlo more on translation ehh. Magsulat ko sang English sentence sa board itranslate ko sa Tagalog, maintindihan nila, so yun lang, so... tapos... tapos yung mga ahh terminologies na gina translate ko sa Tagalog ginatandaan nila (Participant 4, page 2, lines 53-55)</p> <p>overall masasabi ko it's hard teaching Manobo, as a teacher my experience mong mag code switching all the time.... all the time... (Participant 5, page 1, lines 8-9)</p> <p>I have mentioned, I think hindi talaga nila alam yong ibig-sabihin non, yong word na ibinato mo sa kanila, because I think hindi nila alam yong word na yon. They have to know it first in their language and then translate it ganon so that they could know kung ano yong ibig sabihin ng sinabi mo (Participant 5, page 4, lines 153-156)</p> <p>so luckily lang during my time yung grade 2 ako meron akong pupil na almost 12 to or 13 years old so ginawa ko siyang translator no' everytime mag gigive... no? Every time na maggigive-maggigive ako ng instruction, tinatranslate niya (Participant 6, page 1, lines 18-20)</p> <p>iyong mother ay yong trilingual na approach na iManobo mo i use mo ang word na Manobo... then my Filipino siya so tanan translate parang dictionary siya pero tatlo... Filipino then English... then use it in sentence para maintindihan talaga ng bata (Participant 6, page 2, lines 75-78)</p>	<p>Teacher translates or use the learner's mother tongue</p> <p>Teaching English language to Manobo is difficult because you need to translate in their mother tongue.</p> <p>Teacher needs to translate his lessons into the learner's native language</p> <p>Translation is done to elicit responses from these learners</p> <p>Multiple stages of translation, English to Filipino or Ilonggo then relating this to Manobo language</p> <p>Teacher helps students in translating their words into English language</p> <p>Unlocking of terminologies through translation</p> <p>ELT to Manobo is hard because you have to do code-switching all the time.</p> <p>Learners have no knowledge in the target language, so teachers have to translate</p> <p>The need for translator in class</p> <p>You do multiple stages of translation and use it in sentences to ensure understanding of learners.</p>	<p>a. ELT to Manobo requires translation as evident in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of learners' mother tongue • The need to translate lessons into native language • Doing multiple stages of translation <p>b. ELT to Manobo requires translation to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elicit responses from these learners • Help students in translating their words into English language • Unlock terms • Help learners who have no knowledge in the target language <p>c. ELT to Manobo requires translation causing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in teaching due to translation • Difficult ELT experience of teacher to Manobo • The need for class translator

All of them agreed on the use of translation, with some even employing multiple stages of translating to aid comprehension, as shared by P3 and P6.

you have to have some translation, major major translation may from English word and then itranslate mo siya sa Filipino afterwards itranslate mo pa yun siya ng Ilonggo and kung hindi pa rin makuha ng bata you ask them to translate it kung may idea sila what what is that word in their vernacular sa Manobo na language (Participant 3, page 1, lines 5-8)

iyong mother ay yong trilingual na approach na iManobo mo i iuse mo ang word na Manobo... then my Filipino siya so tanan translate parang dictionary siya pero tatlo... Filipino then English... then use it in sentence para maintindihan talaga ng bata (Participant 6, page 2, lines 75-78)

P2, P3, and P4 also shared that they use translation to elicit responses from learners, unlock unfamiliar words, and assist those with little to no knowledge of the target language.

Gaparticipate man sila maam pag na translate mo kinausap mo sila or like magtanong sila sa English sa Manobo yan magparticipate. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 176-177)

you have to have some translation, major major translation may from English word and then itranslate mo siya sa Filipino afterwards itranslate mo pa yun siya ng Ilonggo and kung hindi pa rin makuha ng bata you ask them to translate it kung may idea sila what what is that word in their vernacular sa Manobo na language (Participant 3, page 1, lines 5-8)

mga ahh terminologies na gina translate ko sa Tagalog ginatandaan nila (Participant 4, page 2, lines 53-55)

The language gap between teachers and learners made English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners particularly challenging, especially for non-IP English teachers. P6 even shared that he had a class translator during his early years of teaching.

overall masasabi ko it's hard teaching Manobo, as a teacher my experience mong mag code switching all the time... all the time... (Participant 5, page 1, lines 8-9)

so luckily lang during my time yung grade 2 ako meron akong pupil na almost 12 to or 13 years old so ginawa ko siyang translator no' everytime mag gigive... no? Every time na maggigive-maggigive ako ng instruction, tinatranslate niya (Participant 6, page 1, lines 18-20)

In this study, translation and code-switching emerged as practical and necessary tools in English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners. As Cook (2010) asserts, translation is not a hindrance but a meaningful method that facilitates better understanding of the target language when used appropriately in multilingual contexts.

Subtheme 2. ELT to Manobo needs cultural consideration

Under the framework of culturally responsive teaching, it is essential to adapt English Language Teaching (ELT) to align with the cultural values, traditions, language and lived experiences of Indigenous learners. For the Manobo community, incorporating cultural consideration in ELT ensures that instruction is respectful, relevant, and empowering.

Table 20. Excerpts on ELT to Manobo needs cultural consideration as one of the subthemes on culturally responsive teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
kailangan mabal'an mo kung ano ang cultural beliefs ganun kasi minsan kasi sa kanila maam parang very sensitive sila (Participant 2, page 2, lines 49-50)	As an English language teacher to Manobo learners, you need to know their cultural background since they are sensitive.	a. ELT to Manobo needs cultural consideration due to:
Kung ano yun mga cultural and ano yung doon maam ay a ano yung mga kailangan nila (Participant 2, page 3, lines 117)	Culture and specific needs of Manobo learners are given importance during trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners' sensitivity • Very sensitive learners
ano nalang kaya kung hindi ako marunong mag salita ng Manobo ti hindi nila ...maano maintindihan lesson yung ko... so kung baga okay din yun alam mo din yung dialect nila dahil maka maka share kayo ng knowledge (Participant 2, page 5, lines 204-206)	Familiarity of teachers with the Manobo language is an edge in the teaching-learning process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Familiarity of teachers with the Manobo language is an edge
Using first their lingua la language (Participant 3, page 1, line 43)	Teachers also allow learners to use their first language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to deal with them
For example, mga nasa ano lang siguro, palagay natin mga 10% mga 90% hindi ko na alam yung sinasabi nilang ganon pero, still hindi hindi rin ako naga discourage sa kanila "ayy don't talk amoni-amoni!" Kasi that's their way of expressing themselves so, (Participant 3, page 2, lines 47-49)	Teachers do not discourage the Manobo learners in speaking their language to promote response from the learners	b. ELT to Manobo needs cultural consideration by:
grabe sila ka sensitive. Sensitive kayo sila. (Participant 3, page 10, line 389)	Teacher observed Manobo as very sensitive learners which should be considered in teaching them	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving focus in culture and specific needs of Manobo learners during seminars
kailangan gid coordination with the ano, with the halin sa mga elders didto para sa cultural background na isa na na mga ta, ma ano ma da, ma ano mo dayon ma assess mo dayon as teacher kung paano sila. (Participant 4, page 9, lines 335-337)	Teachers need to be aware of their culture to know how to deal with these learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing use of learners' native language during classes
aim ng IPED is to... ahh.... hindi mawala yung.. kultura ng mga kabataan especially sa mga IP's so yung activities, examples na gagamitin mo doon is yung mga bagay na nandun sa community, so instead na gagamit ka ng "apple" gagamit ka ng "nanas" laughing... is a terminology ng prutas nila doon ahh doon lang sa kanila din (Participant 6, pages 1-2, lines 44-47)	Preservation of culture is observed in delivering lessons as teacher uses examples that are within the community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not discouraging learners to speak their native language
calendar of activities kasi ng Dulangan Manobo may month sila sa pagtatanim paghaharvest so yong activities mo is ma fafall dapat doon, kaya yong lesson plan namin is nirerevise yan namin (Participant 6, page 2, lines 49-51)	Matching their lessons to the Manobo's calendar of activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservation of culture • Using of examples within the community
naka community based pala yong ano nya yong mga activities niya yong mga example na festivities ng community (Participant 6, page 2, lines 57-58)	Learning activities are based on the events within the community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matching their lessons with the learners
Oh, kahit na grade 1, na ano ahhh, naga harvest, naga tulong talaga yan sila, hindi mo man sila pwedi nahhh, sabi nila child labor, ahh, forced labor, pero exempted ang IP jan, pagdating sa ganyan, kultura nila yan eh (Participant 6, page 7, lines 285-287)	Teacher emphasizes that helping their parents in farm is innate in their culture and it can't be labeled as child or force labor.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matching learning activities with the community's events
family source of income nila, na buong pamilya ngatutulong-tulong sila, may values kasi don sa nakukuha, hindi yun siya pinapatrabaho para buhayain niya si nanay to, si tatay matawhay siya maubra, hindi ang taught doon is, a whole family goes to the farm and their harvest, para mapadali yung trabaho (Participant 6, page 7, lines 288-291)	The teacher shares that farming is a shared family activity among Manobo learners, rooted in cultural value of cooperation to ease the work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasizing that helping their parents is innate in their culture and cannot be labeled as child labor • Sharing that farming is a shared activity rooted in their culture

The need for cultural consideration stems from the learners' sensitivity, the idea of knowing your learners in terms of their characteristics and language which will give a teacher an edge in teaching.

kailangan mabal'an mo kung ano ang cultural beliefs ganun kasi minsan kasi sa kanila maam parang very sensitive sila (Participant 2, page 2, lines 49-50)

ano nalang kaya kung hindi ako marunong mag salita ng Manobo ti hindi nila ...maano maintindihan lesson yung ko... so kung baga okay din yun alam mo din yung dialect nila dahil maka maka share kayo ng knowledge (Participant 2, page 5, lines 204-206)

grabe sila ka sensitive. Sensitive kayo sila. (Participant 3, page 10, line 389)

kailangan gid coordination with the ano, with the halin sa mga elders didto para sa cultural background na isa na na mga ta, ma ano ma da, ma ano mo dayon ma assess mo dayon as teacher kung paano sila. (Participant 4, page 9, lines 335-337)

Moreover, the Manobo culture and the specific needs of these learners are emphasized during seminars, as shared by P2. P3 also mentioned allowing her learners to speak in their native language to encourage responses, while P6 emphasized that helping their parents on the farm is an inherent part of their culture and should not be seen as child labor. These practices are highlighted by the participants to respect Manobo culture, with the goal of delivering meaningful lessons to these learners.

Kung ano yun mga cultural and ano yung doon maam ay a ano yung mga kailangan nila (Participant 2, page 3, lines 117)

For example, mga nasa ano lang siguro, palagay natin mga 10% mga 90% hindi ko na alam yung sinasabi nilang ganon pero, still hindi hindi rin ako naga discourage sa kanila "ayy don't talk amoni-amoni!" Kasi that's their way of expressing themselves so, (Participant 3, page 2, lines 47-49)

Oh, kahit na grade 1, na ano ahhh, naga harvest, naga tulong talaga yan sila, hindi mo man sila pwedi nahhh, sabi nila child labor, ahh, forced labor, pero exempted ang IP jan, pagdating sa ganyan, kultura nila yan eh (Participant 6, page 7, lines 285-287)

These insights highlight how cultural knowledge is essential to successful English Language Teaching (ELT) in indigenous contexts. This aligns with Gay (2018), who emphasized that culturally responsive teaching involves understanding students' cultural experiences as essential to effective instruction. In the case of the Manobo learners, respecting their traditions and daily realities fosters trust and engagement in learning.

Subtheme 3. Learner-based teaching

Learner-based instruction emphasizes the importance of centering students' needs, backgrounds, and learning styles. In the context of Manobo learners, this approach encourages active participation and creates meaningful learning experiences by valuing their unique identities and perspectives.

Table 21. Excerpts on Learner-based teaching as one of the subthemes on culturally responsive teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
<p>you need to bend your kwan talaga expectation .. and your approach sa learners para lang makuha talaga nila maam... yong gusto mong ibigay sa kanila... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 70-72).</p> <p>so I adapt... based on their... capabilities din maam yon yong ano.... (Participant 1, page 2, line 81).</p> <p>yes the competencies itself... hindi talaga eh hindi hindi yong kwan eh kung baga ano kay kailangan mo no ano iyong term don....?...kung baga eh contextualized talaga eh contextualized iyong iyong ang CG na yong... yong curriculum na yon na mag suit doon sa needs ng bata pero hindi pa rin dapat mag layo doon eh.. ganoon talaga maam... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 85-88).</p> <p>teaching talaga ma'am yung expectation mo medyo babaan mo. Kasi tulad tulad ng sabi ko..... ideally theoretically ito, but.... yung re real vs. expectation (Participant 1, page 6, lines 227-228).</p> <p>Ahh sa seminar sa akin maam bago lang ako nag seminar ng yung sa ano sa IPED. (Participant 2, page 3, lines 113)</p> <p>So, meron kasing may mga seminar kasi tayo na, IPED ba yun way back 2014 retooling yun siya ma'am, so may retooling, may contextualization... (Participant 3, page 2, lines 57-59)</p> <p>isimplify mo sa kanila which is better ba maiintindihan nila (Participant 3, page 3, lines 91-92)</p> <p>They freely express themselves na, ma'am, ganito ganyan free silang naga tanong. (Participant 3, page 3, lines 115)</p> <p>hadlok daw siya so sabi ko huwag kayong matakot you have to expre ah freely express kung hindi niyo ma express sabi ko sa ano sa now English you have to express it first sa ano sa Filipino kay e allow ko yan (Participant 3, pages 5, lines 213-215)</p> <p>Just be there themselves sabi ko sa kanya iexpress niyo lang sarili niyo (Participant 3, page 7, line 262)</p> <p>binaba ko expectation ko, ang standard ko as teacher para ma-meet ko ang ano nila, ang... standard din nila. (Participant 4, page 1, lines 25-26)</p> <p>ang akon way of teaching... nakafocus na naka... naka-align sa paano sila tudluan ang mga Manobo learners so siguro ang... ang teaching approach ko is base sa pano pagtudlo sa isa ka Manobo (Participant 4, page 2, lines 63-65)</p> <p>(laughs) kung may new Manobo... uh... teacher nga sa Manobo learners... nga... magtudlo sa Manobo learners... lower your expectations and lower your standards noh. (Participant 4, page 8, lines 296-297)</p> <p>yes for curriculum guide may fino-follow tayo na ganon and I cannot follow that na taposin yung kung ano yung mga kailangan kong ito for the first quarter up to fourth quarter, di ko yan lahat matuturo ma'am kasi I have to consider yung capacity ng mga bata (Participant 5, page 4, lines 165-168)</p> <p>hindi tayo mag sunod, hahanap tayo ng paraan kasi iba ang mga mindset ng mga bata dito sa ***** iba ito hindi mo ito, susunod sa level ng mga bata nga nasa labas, iba sila, iba ito medyo late (Participant 6, page 3, lines 126-128)</p> <p>go down mo ang level mo hindi mo iinsist ang teaching strategies mo yung means of instruction mo na istrikto ka doon, na dapat ganon talaga siya, standard talaga siya, hindi hindi yan pwede doon sa IP school, mahihirapan ka, later on masasabi mo sa sarili mo na failure ka, parang hindi mo, hindi ka teacher na marami ka nang negative na maisip (Participant 6, pages 5-6, lines 232-235)</p> <p>so why not go down no, adjust your level of teaching, adjust your objectives into makakaya ng mga bata. (Participant 6, page 6, lines 238-239)</p>	<p>Adjusting expectation and approach with these learners to ensure English language learning</p> <p>Teacher adapts his English language teaching according to his learners' capabilities. Contextualizing lessons to suit the learners' needs without deviating from the prescribed standards</p> <p>You have to lower your expectation with these learners.</p> <p>English language teachers are sent to seminars to gain knowledge in teaching Manobo learners Teachers are sent to IPED seminars to learn contextualizing lessons for Manobo learners</p> <p>Simplifying lessons for Manobo learners to attain understanding</p> <p>Allow students to freely ask and express themselves</p> <p>Creating a safe space where students can express themselves freely in their native language</p> <p>Allowing students to freely express themselves in learning English language</p> <p>Teacher lowers his expectation and standard as a teacher to meet the learners' standard</p> <p>Teachers' way of teaching has become responsive to Manobo learners overtime</p> <p>Teachers should lower their expectations and standards with these learners</p> <p>Deviation from the curriculum guide to consider the learners' capacity</p> <p>Teachers have to tailor their teaching with the learners leading to deviation from curriculum guide</p> <p>You should go down to their level and do not insist your teaching style because it will not work with them and may even bring you negative thoughts.</p> <p>Match your teaching to their level</p>	<p>a. Learner-based teaching through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjusting expectations and teaching approach • Adapting lessons with his learners • Contextualizing lessons based on learners • Lowering expectations with learners • Sending teachers to IPED seminars • Simplifying lessons to attain understanding • Allowing students to freely ask and express themselves • Creating safe space for learning where learners can speak with their native language • Lowering of expectation and standards • Manobo responsive way of teaching • Going down to the learners' level of learning • Deviation from the curriculum to consider the learners' capacity

As P1 shared, learner-based teaching is done through adjusting expectation from these learners and matching your teaching approach with them. P2 added that they are thought on how to contextualize lessons for Manobo learners during seminars.

you need to bend your kwan talaga expectation .. and your approach sa learners para lang makuha talaga nila maam... yong gusto mong ibigay sa kanila... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 70-72).

So, meron kasing may mga seminar kasi tayo na, IPED ba yun way back 2014 retooling yun siya ma'am, so may retooling, may contextualization... (Participant 3, page 2, lines 57-59)

This has been intensified by P3 saying that lessons must be simplified, and learners are allowed or encouraged to freely express themselves to create a safe learning space for Manobo learners.

isimplify mo sa kanila which is better ba maiintindihan nila (Participant 3, page 3, lines 91-92)

They freely express themselves na, ma'am, ganito ganyan free silang naga tanong. (Participant 3, page 3, lines 115)

hadlok daw siya so sabi ko huwag kayong matakot you have to express ah freely express kung hindi niyo ma express sabi ko sa ano sa now English you have to express it first sa ano sa Filipino kay e allow ko yan (Participant 3, pages 5, lines 213-215)

P4 also mentioned that his approach to teaching has significantly changed to better suit the needs of these learners.

ang akon way of teaching... nakafocus na naka... naka-align sa paano sila tudluan ang mga Manobo learners so siguro ang... ang teaching approach ko is base sa pano pagtudlo sa isa ka Manobo (Participant 4, page 2, lines 63-65)

Not only may the teacher's teaching style change, but the competencies outlined in the curriculum guide may also be adjusted or modified to better align with the capacity of these learners, as shared by P1 and P6.

yes the competencies itself... hindi talaga eh hindi hindi yong kwan eh kung бага ano kay kailangan mo no ano iyong term don....?...kung бага eh contextualized talaga eh contextualized iyong iyong ang CG na yong... yong curriculum na yon na mag suit doon sa needs ng bata pero hindi pa rin dapat mag layo doon eh.. ganoon talaga maam... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 85-88).

yes for curriculum guide may fino-follow tayo na ganon and I cannot follow that na taposin yung kung ano yung mga kailangan kong ito for the first quarter up to

fourth quarter, di ko yan lahat matuturo ma'am kasi I have to consider yung capacity ng mga bata (Participant 5, page 4, lines 165-168)

All these experiences align with the view on culturally responsive teaching, which emphasizes modifying instructional strategies based on the cultural and learning backgrounds of students. According to Gay (2010), effective teachers value cultural knowledge, prior experiences, and learning styles of diverse students, adapting their instruction accordingly to make learning more relevant and effective. Hence these teachers are doing the best they could to impart knowledge with these less fortunate learners.

VI. Resourcefulness in Remote Teaching

Figure 8. Schematic Diagram on Resourcefulness in Remote Teaching

Resourcefulness in remote teaching is important, especially when materials and internet access are limited. Using pictures helps students understand lessons, while audio-visual tools make learning more engaging. Additionally, using local resources allows teachers to work with what is available in the community.

Subtheme 1. Maximizing the use of pictures

In teaching English to Manobo learners, teachers often lack textbooks and materials. To address this, they use pictures as visual aids, which, though common in

urban areas, are especially effective for Manobo learners, making lessons more relatable.

Table 22. Excerpts on Maximizing the use of pictures as one of the subthemes on resourcefulness in remote teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
puro lang ako picture picture... ganoon ahh printed ganon lang ma'am (Participant 1, page 1, lines 26-27).	They often use pictures or other printer materials as visual aids.	a. Resourcefulness in remote teaching through maximizing the use of pictures due to:
iyong pinaka nakikita naming effective doon maam iyong pictures pictures talaga as pictures associa... iassociate mo maam ganun or mas kasi ganun e eh malayo talaga sa kwan maam kung baga picture lang iyan pero sa kanila parang wow parang tv parang tv na sa kanila yon maam iyong makakita lang sila ng pictures na makulay parang sa sa atin parang naga tingin na tayo sa tv ba television para naga iyon na iyong perception nila ba sa... (Participant 1, page 3, lines 105-109).	Teacher describes pictures as an effective learning material in ELT to Manobo. Learners are amazed by it and even perceive it as a television.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited teaching resources available • Effectivity of this learning material for teaching Manobo learners • Learners being amazed by pictures • Even perceive it as TV
nagagawa rin ako ng mga... naga-print rin ako dito sa baba. Naga-print ako ng pictures para ma... ma-support ko yung... ideas ba. Para mas maka-imagine sila (Participant 4, page 1, lines 35-37)	Teachers print pictures back home to support learners' imagination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support learners' imagination • Its function as the best IMs for Manobo learners
regarding with the teaching materials ahh na effective sya yung word picture ang unang-unang ginamit ko non because we have no facilities pa during that time (Participant 6, page 1, lines 27-28)	Pictures are effective teaching materials with these learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being lightweight which is ideal for long hikes or rides to schools
ang the best na ginamit namin doon is yung pic picture word (Participant 6, page 1, lines 31-32)	Teacher describes picture as the best teaching materials for these learners	
Flashcards... yan nalang maam yong ma'am maam... yong magagaan lang kasi sa **** to school ko 2 hours more than 2 hours paakyat ng bundok so hindi	Teacher relies on lightweight resources such as flashcards which are more manageable	

din pwede ang mabibigat. for long hikes or rides to
(Participant 1, page 3, lines 97-98). the school.

P1 explained that printed pictures became the go-to instructional material. With very limited access to standard teaching resources, they relied heavily on visuals to communicate meaning and make lessons more engaging for the learners.

*puro lang ako picture picture... ganoon ahh printed ganon lang ma'am
(Participant 1, page 1, lines 26-27).*

iyong pinaka nakikita naming effective doon maam iyong pictures... pictures talaga as pictures associa... iassociate mo maam ganun or mas kasi ganun e eh malayo talaga sa kwan maam kung baga picture lang iyan pero sa kanila parang wow parang tv parang tv na sa kanila yon maam iyong makakita lang sila ng pictures na makulay parang sa sa atin parang naga tingin na tayo sa tv ba television para naga iyon na iyong perception nila ba sa... (Participant 1, page 3, lines 105-109).

P1 further described how pictures captivate Manobo learners, noting that colorful visuals are perceived with excitement—almost like watching a television. This shows how even simple printed images can become powerful tools to spark curiosity and learning.

nagagawa rin ako ng mga... naga-print rin ako dito sa baba. Naga-print ako ng pictures para ma... ma-support ko yung... ideas ba. Para mas maka-imagine sila (Participant 4, page 1, lines 35-37)

P4 shared that visuals are not just used for decoration but to help students form mental images of new concepts and P6 described pictures as the best teaching materials for this type of remote teaching.

ang the best na ginamit namin doon is yung pic picture word (Participant 6, page 1, lines 31-32)

P3 also mentioned on the use of lightweight teaching materials such as flashcards which are more manageable for long hikes or rides to the school.

*Flashcards... yan nalang maam yong ma'am maam... yong magagaan lang kasi sa **** to school ko 2 hours more than 2 hours paakyat ng bundok so hindi din pwede ang mabibigat. (Participant 1, page 3, lines 97-98).*

These classroom experiences reflect what Diez (2024) found in his study on curriculum delivery in Bukidnon Jesuit Mission Schools, where educators also taught Indigenous learners in low-resource environments. The study emphasized the strategic use of simple yet meaningful tools—like printed visuals—to convey lessons

effectively. When teachers adapt to their context with creativity and purpose, even the most basic materials can yield strong educational outcomes.

Subtheme 2. Maximizing the use of audio-visual

Audio-visual materials serve as powerful tools to support learning. While such aids may be considered ordinary in urban classrooms, they can have a significant impact on Manobo learners by making lessons more engaging, accessible, and easier to understand in remote and resource-limited contexts.

Table 23. Excerpts on Maximizing the use of audio-visual as one of the subthemes on resourcefulness in remote teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
pag may chance minsan sa mga kwan sabi ko film viewing English para ano ma'am ah ma kwan gud nila ma'am ma maappreciate nila ang English or ano... para lang ma kwan nila ma'am maa malove nila or ma ano ma kahit papano. (Participant 1, page 5, lines 195-198).	Teacher utilizes film viewing to these learners for them to appreciate the language	a. Resourcefulness in remote teaching through maximizing the use of audio-visual aids by means of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Film viewings to appreciate the language
through internet ay ano na Audio Visual (Participant 2, page 2, lines 57)	Teachers use audio-visual aids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of audio-visual aids
Yung sa videos maam like mga sto...stories na may mga translated into Manobo na mga kwento gud. (Participant 2, page 2, lines 59-60)	Teachers use videos translated in Manobo language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos translated in Manobo language
Interesado naman sila maam ohh pag... hehehe mayroon na akong ano pinapakita na audio-visual presentation. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 192-193)	Teacher finds these learners interested in audio-visual presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of laptops
pag may audio visual na maam nakikinig talaga yan sila maam. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 196-197)	They listen once audio-visual aids are utilized.	b. Resourcefulness in remote teaching through maximizing the use of audio-visual aids due to:
may tv mas maganda yung ganong approach na gagamitin mo especially when you have your television na nakikita ng bata, at the same time gumagalaw, nakikita nila yung mga bagay-bagay na dinidescribe mo in English, especially yung mga.. cars, trains, airplanes, kasi hindi nila alam talaga yan eh doon sa kanila sa community nila. (Participant 6, page 1, lines 38-42)	The use of television is also good because they could see those things that are not available in their community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners' interest in audio-visual presentations • Listen once audio-visual is used • They could see things that are not in their community.

audio visual naipasok ko na rin diyan Audio visual aids were
audio visual na ano kasi kung later on also used later when
nagkakaroon na kami ng yung may laptops were available
mga laptop na na issue (Participant 6,
page 3, lines 97-98)

P1 shared that film viewing in English is sometimes used as a strategy to develop learners' appreciation and interest in the language. This indicates that audio-visual materials are not merely for instruction, but also a tool for cultivating an emotional connection with English.

pag may chance minsan sa mga kwan sabi ko film viewing English para ano ma'am ah ma kwan gud nila ma'am ma maappreciate nila ang English or ano... para lang ma kwan nila ma'am maa malove nila or ma ano ma kahit papano. (Participant 1, page 5, lines 195-198).

Moreover, P2 observed that students show increased interest when audio-visual presentations are included in class.

Interesado naman sila maam ohh pag... hehehe mayroon na akong ano pinapakita na audio-visual presentation. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 192-193)

pag may audio visual na maam nakikinig talaga yan sila maam. (Participant 2, page 5, lines 196-197)

This teacher emphasized the effectiveness of using television to show real-world objects unfamiliar to learners due to their isolated setting.

may tv mas maganda yung ganong approach na gagamitin mo especially when you have your television na nakikita ng bata, at the same time gumagalaw, nakikita nila yung mga bagay-bagay na dinidescibe mo in English, especially yung mga.. cars, trains, airplanes, kasi hindi nila alam talaga yan eh doon sa kanila sa community nila. (Participant 6, page 1, lines 38-42)

These insights reflect the findings of Abdul Samat & Abdul Aziz (2020), who emphasized the importance engaging resources in language teaching for Indigenous learners. In his research on multimedia-supported instruction in remote communities, he concluded that audio-visual aids significantly enhance comprehension, particularly when they reflect learners' lived experiences or introduce new concepts in relatable ways. The use of technology—when paired with cultural sensitivity—can make English more accessible and less intimidating for Indigenous learners like the Manobo.

Subtheme 3. Maximizing local resources

In teaching English to Manobo learners, limited access to electricity, internet, and conventional materials leads teachers to rely on locally available resources. By using realia and elements from the environment, they help learners connect words with real-life experiences and strengthen understanding.

Table 24. Excerpts on Maximizing the use of local resources as one of the subthemes on resourcefulness in remote teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Real objects din ma'am (Participant 2, page 2, lines 68) ahh kung ano lang ang available sa environment doon doon sa school yun lang yung pwede mong, ahh parang, di mo pwedeng ituturo yung mga train! Ano pa ba jan? Yung mga bus kasi di man nila yan makikita, mga kalesa yan ano pa ba? Sa howling ng kabayo yun yung i-example mo talaga doon sa kanilang ano. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 59-61)	Teacher also uses real objects Teacher uses examples that are within the environment so learners could easily grasp the idea	a. Maximizing local resources in ELT to Manobo as evident in: • Use of real objects • Examples within the environment
Localization so kung ano yung available sa kanyang, sa kanilang environment (Participant 3, page 2, lines 67-68) Walang- walang kuryente ma'am, walang internet. Lahat... ano talaga... (laugh) Imaginative, ano tas... More on, ano, realia, yung... kung ano makita sa paligid, yun lang. May mga- may marinig ka na huni ng ibon. Tanungin mo kung anong ibon yun, tas anong ibon sa English. Ganun- ganun lang! (Participant 4, page 1, lines 28-31)	Use examples that are within the environment Since there is no electricity, teachers use realia	• Use of realia • Examples within the classroom
I've said no realia talaga no, kung ano lang yung makita na... na... mga... mga gamit sa... sa school sa loob ng classroom (Participant 4, page 1, lines 34-35)	Use of realia and other things inside the classroom	

P2 emphasized the importance of using tangible materials in instruction, a point supported by P4, who also added that he uses examples found within the school environment due to the lack of electricity.

Real objects din ma'am (Participant 2, page 2, lines 68)

Walang- walang kuryente ma'am, walang internet. Lahat... ano talaga... (laugh) Imaginative, ano tas... More on, ano, realia, yung... kung ano makita sa paligid, yun lang. May mga- may marinig ka na huni ng ibon. Tanungin mo kung anong ibon yun, tas anong ibon sa English. Ganun- ganun lang! (Participant 4, page 1, lines 28-31)

I've said no realia talaga no, kung ano lang yung makita na... na... mga... mga gamit sa... sa school sa loob ng classroom (Participant 4, page 1, lines 34-35)

Moreover, P3 shared about tailoring examples to the learners' immediate surroundings, ensuring that lessons are relatable and comprehensible. The emphasis on localization is further reinforced.

ahh kung ano lang ang available sa environment doon doon sa school yun lang yung pwede mong, ahh parang, di mo pwedeng ituturo yung mga train! Ano pa ba jan? Yung mga bus kasi di man nila yan makikita, mga kalesa yan ano pa ba? Sa howling ng kabayo yun yung i-example mo talaga doon sa kanilang ano. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 59-61)

Localization so kung ano yung available sa kanyang, sa kanilang environment (Participant 3, page 2, lines 67-68)

A related study by Setiadi (2011) supports this approach. The research investigated the effectiveness of using realia in improving students' vocabulary mastery. The study found that incorporating real objects into English lessons significantly enhanced students' vocabulary acquisition, engagement, and retention. This approach aligns with the experiences of teachers working with Manobo learners, emphasizing the importance of contextual and tangible teaching materials in language instruction.

VII. Teachers' Motivation in Teaching

Figure 9. Schematic Diagram on Teachers' Motivation in Teaching

Teachers' motivation in teaching plays a big role in the success of education. One source of this motivation is fulfillment in learners' progress, as seeing students grow and improve brings a sense of achievement. Another source is fulfillment in learners' appreciation, which makes teachers feel valued and inspired to continue their work. These forms of fulfillment help keep teachers passionate and committed to their teaching.

Subtheme 1. Fulfillment in learners' progress

Witnessing learners' growth and improvement serves as a strong source of personal and professional fulfillment. For teachers working with Manobo students, each sign of progress—no matter how small—reinforces their commitment and sense of purpose, especially in challenging and underserved teaching environments. These moments of progress affirm the value of their efforts and encourage them to continue despite the difficulties. They also foster deeper connections with learners, making the teaching experience more meaningful and rewarding.

Table 25. Excerpts on Fulfillment in learners' progress as one of the subthemes on teachers' motivation in teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
<p>iyon iyong best experience na sabi yong yong kahit papaano na napapalitan ko sila na no hindi dapat ganyan kasi dapat ganito... ah kaya kaya nung sil punta muna kami ng balanggay eh kahit iyong mga basic ahh... iyong mga daily used ah kwan nila ah at least kahit papaano na titwist namin oh na aalign namin ah kung what is kung ano iyong dapat. (Participant 1, page 1, lines 39-43).</p>	<p>Teachers express gratification when they are able to correct or improve the learners' pronunciation</p>	<p>a. Fulfillment in learners' progress as shown in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers' gratification when learners are improving Motivated teaching Teachers view of themselves as important in the transfer of knowledge
<p>Basta maging proficient lang silaaa, successful na yun para saakin. Kagaya nun yung sabi ko na wow, before wala talaga ito may sulat, ngayon marami na to. Diba, rew, kwan siya sa akin, parang successful ka as a teacher for them. (Participant 3, page 8, lines 320-322)</p>	<p>Teacher views learners' progress or proficiency as their way of succeeding as a teacher</p>	<p>b. Fulfillment in learners' progress because they see it as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Their way of succeeding as teachers An achievement as a teacher Source of motivation Something to look forward
<p>makita mo sa mukha ng bata, ng estudyante may natutunan sila sa imo so that alone maka motivate, dako na nga motivation para sa akin para mag continue teach sa Manobo learners. (Participant 4, page 7, lines 237-239)</p>	<p>Learners' progress fuels motivation among teachers to continue teaching them.</p>	<p>c. Fulfillment in learners' progress because they lead to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fueling teachers' motivation to continue teaching Motivating themselves in having learners competing for English competitions
<p>ma amaze ko kay yun nga maka mas maganahan ka magtudlo, labin na tung gina tudluan mo may natutunan kahit papaano sa'yo. (Participant 4, page 7, lines 240-242)</p>	<p>Teachers are motivated to teach when learners are having progress</p>	
<p>my learners pa rin ma'am kasi feeling ko, feeling ko it is an achievement, to see your learners excel in English knowing that, kilala mo sila as hindi marunong mag ano, as, as, as a zero. (Participant 5, page 5, lines 184-186)</p>	<p>Teacher described it as an achievement if learners are excelling</p>	
<p>That's my motivation, dapat by by the end of the school year, meron akong bata na may ikocompete sa baba. oumoh...in English competition (Participant 5, page 5, lines 190-192)</p>	<p>Teachers' motivation to compete a student in English competitions</p>	
<p>I won't stop din talaga, I won't stop up until na in the run of my teaching in the department of education I could see or I will see in the future one of my students excelling in English din so it would be an immeasurable happiness for me to see that such situation my student before, my former student seeing him excelling in his chosen career is I think an achievement. (Participant 5, page 6, lines 232-236)</p>	<p>The success of learners has become the source of motivation of teachers.</p>	
<p>nakikita mo rin sa mga bata later on na maghahighschool na hindi man siya ma left behind in terms of English. (Participant 6, page 4, lines 146-147)</p>	<p>Seeing your learners progress in learning English</p>	
<p>So, motivation yan sakin na ay sige mag duty talaga ako kay ano kailangan nila ako marami pang dapat matutunan so yun siya ma'am (Participant 3, page 8, lines 307-308)</p>	<p>Teacher is motivated by seeing herself important in transferring knowledge to her students</p>	

Teachers' gratification when learners are improving, motivated teaching, and viewing themselves as important in the transfer of knowledge are just some of the manifestations of their success as teachers which fuels them to continue teaching these Manobo learners as recounted by P1, P3, and P4

iyon iyong best experience na sabi yong yong kahit papaano na napapalitan ko sila na no hindi dapat ganyan kasi dapat ganito... ah kaya kaya nung sil punta muna kami ng balanggay eh kahit iyong mga basic ahh... iyong mga daily used ah kwan nila ah at least kahit papaano na titwist namin oh na aalign namin ah kung what is kung ano iyong dapat. (Participant 1, page 1, lines 39-43).

Basta maging proficient lang silaaa, successful na yun para sakin. Kagaya nun yung sabi ko na wow, before wala talaga ito may sulat, ngayon marami na to. Diba, rew, kwan siya sa akin, parang successful ka as a teacher for them. (Participant 3, page 8, lines 320-322)

makita mo sa mukha ng bata, ng estudyante may natutunan sila sa imo so that alone maka motivate, dako na nga motivation para sa akin para mag continue teach sa Manobo learners. (Participant 4, page 7, lines 237-239)

This has been intensified by P5 saying that his learner's success has become his source of motivation in teaching.

I won't stop din talaga, I won't stop up until na in the run of my teaching in the department of education I could see or I will see in the future one of my students excelling in English din so it would be an immeasurable happiness for me to see that such situation my student before, my former student seeing him excelling in his chosen career is I think an achievement. (Participant 5, page 6, lines 232-236)

This sense of satisfaction stemming from visible learner improvement reflects what Nalipay et al. (2019) describe as the emotional satisfaction teachers feel when their students achieve milestones, reinforcing their sense of purpose. It is a quiet but deeply felt joy—one that makes the long hours and tireless effort feel undeniably worthwhile.

Subtheme 2. Fulfillment in learners' appreciation

Receiving appreciation from learners can be a deeply rewarding experience. For educators teaching Manobo students, gestures of gratitude—whether verbal or expressed through active participation—affirm their efforts and strengthen their dedication to teaching in culturally and geographically challenging contexts.

Table 26. Excerpts on Fulfillment in learners' appreciation as one of the subthemes on teachers' motivation in teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Yun, gina-appreciate ka nila that is rewarding. (Participant 3, page 8, line 310)	Feeling rewarded by learners' appreciation	Fulfillment in learners' appreciation as they feel: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rewarded by learners' appreciation • Touched by learners' letters
binasa ko yong mga ano nila yong mga letters na isinulat nila parang somehow na touch ako yes na da ana touch talaga ako kasi sabi nila sa akin...ahhhm... thank you so much daw (Participant 5, page 2, lines 72-74)	Teacher is touched by the learner' thank you letters	

P3 and P5 shared feeling rewarded and touched by learners' appreciation, especially through heartfelt letters, which fueled their dedication to teaching.

Yun, gina-appreciate ka nila that is rewarding. (Participant 3, page 8, line 310)

binasa ko yong mga ano nila yong mga letters na isinulat nila parang somehow na touch ako yes na da ana touch talaga ako kasi sabi nila sa akin...ahhhm... thank you so much daw (Participant 5, page 2, lines 72-74)

These affirmations from students and the community reflect a deep sense of respect, making the teacher feel valued. According to Nalipay et al. (2019), such emotional feedback plays a significant role in maintaining teacher resilience, particularly in culturally diverse settings.

VIII. Purposeful Teaching

Figure 10. Schematic Diagram on Purposeful Teaching

Purposeful teaching in English Language Teaching to Manobo learners means teaching with clear goals and strong dedication. It starts with emphasizing the importance of learning English language to help learners see its value. Teachers also encourage learners and serve as the key to English learning for Manobo learners. This also involves extra effort of teachers in ELT to Manobo and a focus on teachers' long-term goal for Manobo learners, aiming for their continued growth and success.

Subtheme 1. Emphasizing importance of learning English language

Helping Manobo learners see the value of English can inspire them to dream bigger and reach farther. When we show them that learning English is not about leaving their roots behind, but about adding to who they already are, we build both their confidence and their future.

Table 27. Excerpts on Emphasizing the importance of learning English language as one of the subthemes on purposeful teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
<p>First uhh unang una inexplain ko sa kanila that our the medium of instruction should be English kasi English tayo uhm sa math pwede ko pa yang itwist (Participant 1, page 4, lines 171-172).</p>	<p>Teacher reiterates the importance of using English language as the medium of instruction</p>	<p>a. Emphasizing the importance of learning English language because:</p>
<p>so mino motivate ko nalang na not all the time yun na pumapasok nalang dun yung sabi ko sa kanila na hindi naman kasi all the time mag ha high school pa kayo mag ka college pa kayo at the same time haharapin nyu yung totoong buhay sabi ko hindi lahat ng panahon at tsaka pag gaw labas niyo hindi pwede na Manobo lang din or Tagalog lang din yung sasabihin ninyo or babasahin ninyo dun sa daan mostly sabi ko kay that's my motivation yung the yung the lifelong learning na kumbaga ma'am na they encountered everyday na paglabas ba naman ninyo hindi yung nakasulat sa signs sa mga stores sa mga directions is not Manobo, not all the time Tagalog. Minsan mas marami pa ngang English so when you encountered that sabi ko kahit man lang mga simple English like "slowdown" oh naga drive ka ng motor then you pass "slowdown" (Participant 1, page 5, lines 183-191).</p>	<p>Teacher instills practical applications of English language in real life situations to motivate the learners in learning the language.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is the medium of instruction for English subject • It's useful in dealing with real life situations • Its importance in daily lives. • It is a major subject • Used in global conversations • For future purposes such as going to other countries
<p>ini emphasized ko sa kanila na mahalaga talaga ang English kay kahit kahit sabihin nyu na ayaw nyu ng English but in the end of the day sabi ko ah hanggang hangga't (laughing) nabubuhay tayo hangga't nakikipag salamuha tayo sa tao magagamit at magagamit natin ang English kaya yun yung motivation ko sa kanila ma'am (Participant 1, page 5, lines 192-195).</p>	<p>Teacher motivates the learners through emphasizing the importance of English language in our daily lives</p>	
<p>English ito ha major subject so kailangan niyo ibigay niyo ang best memorize niyo gid na dapat (Participant 3, page 7, lines 290-291)</p>	<p>Reminding students to give their best because English is a major subject</p>	
<p>... parang ang kuwan ko sila halimbawa, you are in a certain place tapos English lang yung gagamitin kasi sa other country, ganun so how can you deal with those people, kung di ka makakabalo mag inEnglish, so you have to speak English, kaya nga you have to learn mga basic conversation nga using English, so you have to think English lahat ang bagay na sa paligid mo ang English isipin mo anong English nito, ganito, ganito na mga bagay so ganun siya kasi kung hindi ka marunong, hindi ka talaga makakapunta (Participant 3, page 9, lines 364-369)</p>	<p>Teacher motivates these learners in learning English language so they could engage into global conversations</p>	
<p>hindi kayo forever na dito lang no baba baba din kayo so... basic kahit basic English lang matutunan natin... at least kahit pa paano maka maka ano gyapon ta so yun parang makita mo din na ma motivate mo sila ma encourage din sila so more on more on... giving advice pieces of advice (Participant 4, page 8, lines 274-277)</p>	<p>Teacher motivates and encourages her students to learn even basic English, reminding them they won't stay in the same place forever.</p>	

Teaching English to Manobo learners involves more than just instruction—it is about building meaningful motivation rooted in real-life application and long-term relevance. P1 emphasized the foundational importance of English as a medium of instruction:

First uhh unang una inexplain ko sa kanila that our the medium of instruction should be English kasi English tayo uhm sa math pwede ko pa yang itwist (Participant 1, page 4, lines 171-172)

P1 drew connections between English learning and everyday life, encouraging students to see its practical value beyond the classroom. He shared that real-life exposure to signs, directions, and interactions makes learning English necessary.

ini emphasized ko sa kanila na mahalaga talaga ang English kay kahit kahit sabihin nyu na ayaw nyu ng English but in the end of the day sabi ko ah hanggang hangga't (laughing) nabubuhay tayo hangga't nakikipag salamuha tayo sa tao magagamit at magagamit natin ang English kaya yun yung motivation ko sa kanila ma'am (Participant 1, page 5, lines 192-195).

so mino motivate ko nalang na not all the time yun na pumapasok nalang dun yung sabi ko sa kanila na hindi naman kasi all the time mag ha high school pa kayo mag ka college pa kayo at the same time haharapin nyu yung totoong buhay sabi ko hindi lahat ng panahon at tsaka pag gaw labas niyo hindi pwede na Manobo lang din or Tagalog lang din yung sasabihin ninyo or babasahin ninyo dun sa daan mostly sabi ko kay that's my motivation yung the yung the lifelong learning na kumbaga ma'am na they encountered everyday na paglabas ba naman ninyo hindi yung nakasulat sa signs sa mga stores sa mga directions is not Manobo, not all the time Tagalog. Minsan mas marami pa ngang English so when you encountered that sabi ko kahit man lang mga simple English like "slowdown" oh naga drive ka ng motor then you pass "slowdown" (Participant 1, page 5, lines 183-191).

P3 and P4 emphasized the importance of English language learning among Manobo learners by presenting it as both an academic responsibility and a preparation for global engagement.

English ito ha major subject so kailangan niyo ibigay niyo ang best memorize niyo gid na dapat (Participant 3, page 7, lines 290-291)

... parang ang kuwan ko sila halimbawa, you are in a certain place tapos English lang yung gagamitin kasi sa other country, ganun so how can you deal with those people, kung di ka makakabalo mag inEnglish, so you have to speak English, kaya nga you have to learn mga basic conversation nga using English, so you have to think English lahat ang bagay na sa paligid mo ang English isipin mo anong English nito, ganito, ganito na mga bagay so ganun siya kasi kung hindi ka marunong, hindi ka talaga makakapunta (Participant 3, page 9, lines 364-369)

Finally, encouragement often comes through simple advice grounded in hope for their future mobility:

hindi kayo forever na dito lang no baba baba din kayo so... basic kahit basic English lang matutunan natin... at least kahit pa paano maka maka ano gyapon ta so yun parang makita mo din na ma motivate mo sila ma encourage din sila so more on more on... giving advice pieces of advice (Participant 4, page 8, lines 274-277)

These insights mirror the findings of Obida and Cagoco Jr. (2025), who found that teachers in IP schools adapt their strategies to accommodate cultural and linguistic differences. Their study highlights that understanding learners' backgrounds and being intentional in motivating them are key elements in delivering English lessons effectively, especially in Indigenous contexts.

Subtheme 2. Encourage learners

Encouragement helps Manobo learners overcome self-doubt and build confidence in their abilities. By recognizing their efforts and providing consistent support, teachers help them develop a positive sense of identity within the classroom.

Table 28. Excerpts on Encourage learners as one of the subthemes on purposeful teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
so dapat ma ano mo gid sila maam iencourage mo sila nga hindi ka lang hindi ka lang na asta dira huwag mong sabihin na Manobo ahh Manobo ako nga Manobo lang ako, kundi sabihin mo na ay iencourage mo sila na pare pareho tayong tao kung kung kaya ng iba kaya niyo rin ahh kaya natin.. (Participant 2, page 2, lines 50-53)	Teacher encourages Manobo learners not to think lowly of themselves and that we are all the same and are capable of doing things	a. Encouraging learners Teachers encourage Manobo learners to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not to think lowly of themselves • Think that we are all the same and capable of doing things
mahuya gud usahay ma'am pero gina encourage ko, hindi kamu mahuya ah. (Participant 2, page 4, lines 131-132)	Teachers encourage these reserved learners to be confident	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be confident and not stay as reserved learners • Be a better version of themselves
then of course molding their ano their minds na maging better version ng kanilang sarili, so ayun sya. Mag hopes and mag dreams ganun. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 73-75)	Teacher promotes English language learning through encouraging them to be better version of themselves, and to hope and dream as learners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hope and dream as learners

One teacher observed how some students internalize a sense of inferiority because of their background, and so must be reassured of their equal worth:

so dapat ma ano mo gid sila maam iencourage mo sila nga hindi ka lang hindi ka lang na asta dira huwag mong sabihin na Manobo ahh Manobo ako nga Manobo lang ako, kundi sabihin mo na ay iencourage mo sila na pare pareho tayong tao kung kung kaya ng iba kaya niyo rin ahh kaya natin.. (Participant 2, page 2, lines 50-53)

Another teacher emphasized the importance of helping learners envision a better version of themselves by nurturing hopes and dreams:

then of course molding their ano their minds na maging better version ng kanilang sarili, so ayun sya. Mag hopes and mag dreams ganun. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 73-75)

These statements show how encouragement in language learning is not only academic—it's emotional and aspirational. When learners believe in their capacity, they begin to invest in their growth and see English not as an impossible task, but as a tool for reaching their potential.

This aligns with the findings of Pedroso et al. (2023), who revealed that contextualized strategies—including personalized encouragement—help Indigenous learners feel valued and supported. Their research shows that fostering confidence through culturally responsive methods increases engagement and motivation among IP students, especially when tackling subjects like English that may feel foreign or intimidating.

Subtheme 3. Teachers as the key to English Learning for Manobo Learners

The teaching-learning process in Manobo communities heavily depends on teachers, who are the primary source of knowledge and guidance. In the absence of abundant resources, teachers play a crucial role in both educating and mentoring students, helping them navigate both academic and cultural challenges.

P3 emphasized the teachers' role as the main source of knowledge when teaching Manobo learners in remote areas, where there is limited access to electronic technology and electricity. In these settings, teachers are not only educators but also key figures who provide both academic and practical support, helping bridge the gap between the learners and the target language.

lahat-lahat kay ikaw yung main source ng information doon sa kanila (Participant 3, page 2, lines 66)

main source talaga ng information yung teacher kasi nga wala silang television doon walang kuryente so lahat ikaw talaga. Kahit anong sabihin mo tama ka talaga (Participant 3, page 2, lines 75-77)

Table 29. Excerpts on Teachers as the key to English learning for Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on purposeful teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
lahat-lahat kay ikaw yung main source ng information doon sa kanila (Participant 3, page 2, lines 66)	Teachers are the main source of knowledge	a. Teachers become the key to English learning for Manobo learners as they are described as the:
main source talaga ng information yung teacher kasi nga wala silang television doon walang kuryente so lahat ikaw talaga. Kahit anong sabihin mo tama ka talaga (Participant 3, page 2, lines 75-77)	Teacher becomes the main source of knowledge due to lack of technology and electricity	
ah para sa akin no parang ako iyong ano nila taga bukas ng kanilang isipan noh para into new world of English gani nga from their knowledge na Manobo tagalog lang so napasok ngayon si English para may another naman ...mundo na papasukan... mga discovery na mga terminologies... (Participant 4, page 1, lines 16-18)	Teacher becomes learning gateway for the new world of English language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main source of knowledge due to lack of technology and electricity • Learning gateway for the world of English language • Guide learners in every step of writing activities • Instrument in learning this new language • Gradually exposing learners to modern world • Learning is dependent to teachers in schools
magsulat sang my autobiography ana gud activity so may autobiography...kailangan isulat mo tanan...(giggles)...ang isulat nalang nila ang ila pangalan (Participant 4, page 3, lines 74-79)	Teacher guides learners in every step of writing activities	
Siguro...parang ano, parang tool, parang instrument nila ako may na para daw gateway nila para sa ano maka may sa new learning experience in English (Participant 4, page 6, lines 218-219)	Teacher becomes instrument in learning this new language for Manobo learners	b. Teacher become the key to English language learning for Manobo learners due to:
para hinay-hinayon gyapon, parang isama sila sa, sa new world ganon, sa modern world kay medyo ano gid sila, layo. (Participant 4, page 9, lines 327-328)	Teachers gradually expose Manobo learners to modern world	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of electricity and internet • Working at young age • Going home tired from work • Parents with no educational background
paano matuto magbasa sina kung didto kasa farm, diba? So pag-abot mo sa balay kapoy ang bata, ang nanay non-reader, di kabalo magsulat, so pag-abot sa skwelahan, dependent ang family, ang bata dependent na gid didto sa school (Participant 6, page 6, lines 265-267)	They work at their farms, go home tired, their parents are non-reader or cannot write leading learners to be dependent in school in learning	

Learners are also highly dependent on teachers during English writing activities, requiring thorough guidance to develop their skills, as shared by P4. This close support ensures that learners can understand writing techniques and overcome challenges they face in expressing themselves clearly.

magsulat sang my autobiography ana gud activity so may autobiography...kailangan isulat mo tanan...(giggles)...ang isulat nalang nila ang ila pangalan (Participant 4, page 3, lines 74-79)

He also described himself as in instrument in learning English language which is new to these learners and from that eventually exposing them to the modern world.

Siguro...parang ano, parang tool, parang instrument nila ako may na para daw gateway nila para sa ano maka may sa new learning experience in English (Participant 4, page 6, lines 218-219)

para hinay-hinayon gyapon, parang isama sila sa, sa new world ganon, sa modern world kay medyo ano gid sila, layo. (Participant 4, page 9, lines 327-328)

It is also important to consider P6's statement that these learners are school-dependent, as they return home tired from working on the farm, and their parents, who have no educational background, are unable to support or follow up on their learning at home.

paano matuto magbasa sina kung didto kasa farm, diba? So pag-abot mo sa balay kapoy ang bata, ang nanay non-reader, di kabalo magsulat, so pag-abot sa skwelahan, dependent ang family, ang bata dependent na gid didto sa school (Participant 6, page 6, lines 265-267)

As Nalipay et al. (2019) highlighted, teachers in remote or rural areas are often the only sources of formal knowledge for their students, emphasizing the pivotal role they play in shaping their learners' education. As such, a teacher be prepared—both mentally and professionally—to shoulder this responsibility, knowing that your presence might be a learner's only consistent access to structured learning.

Subtheme 4. Extra effort of teachers in ELT to Manobo

Teachers go beyond the usual demands of instruction by adapting lessons, creating relevant materials, and addressing the unique needs of Manobo learners. They often extend their services, providing extra lessons or individualized support to ensure students' progress. This dedication reflects a deep sense of responsibility and intentionality in making education meaningful and effective despite limited resources. Teachers strive to create an inclusive learning environment that respects cultural differences while empowering students to succeed.

Table 30. Excerpts on Extra effort of teachers in ELT to Manobo as one of the subthemes on purposeful teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Parang yong nakasanayan tapos sabi ko para ako lang man ang gasagot dyan sa inyong ano ba pero at least may improvement daily may makikita ka namang improvement ay naka construct siya ng ganoong ano ng sentence ng yan pala yong tinatanong niya kanina (Participant 3, pages 5-6, lines 217-220) uhh details, naka... ano nagid naka... daw ang isulat nila ang ila information ba... Itagalogon mo pa na kay hindi nila na maintindihan kay nag nag prepare na sila sang papel ahh.. ano yan sir <i>da katiig sir</i> di di namin yan alam ang ahh.. my name is ahh.. ganito ganyan oh anong pangalan nyo name (Participant 4, page 3, lines 81-84)	Teacher observed daily improvements in learners' sentence construction with teachers' guidance	a. Extra effort of Teachers in ELT to Manobo
ana daw spoon-feeding kung sobra pa sa spoon-feeding ana gid man. (Participant 4, page 3, lines 85-86)	Teacher does extra effort when having writing activities. They must write all the details, so learners only have to provide their personal details and translate it so learners could understand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extra effort in guiding learners during writing activities • Putting all the details in writing activities • Learners only need to write their personal details • Even translate it so learners could understand • Do spoon feeding • Doing trilingual approach in translation • Sacrifice for learners • Extending effort and services
sa mga far-flung schools din naman kasi talaga, we lack resources. So... ang masasabi ko is it's upon the teacher na rin talaga to do the effort no (Participant 5, page 2, lines 44-45)	Teachers need to spoon feed	b. They make extra effort because:
It it's upon the effort of the teacher and sa interest pa rin talaga ng bata (Participant 5, page 3, lines 85-86)	Teacher notes that limited resources in remote schools require extra effort to support learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They want their learners to understand and learn • Learning depends on them
so ikaw na teacher... sacrifice ka talaga.. gagawin mo lahat kahit na yong mga approach na hindi na ginagamit sa DepEd..gagawin mo kasi halimbawa yong triling approach (Participant 6, page 2, lines 69-70)	He notes that learning depends on both the teacher's effort and the learner's interest	
So ang ginagawa namin na noon, during that time pa, gumawa kami ng bahay jan sa school, to in order to house yung mga malalayo, so pag-gabi gin tutoran na siya, yung mga...mga mga mga lagyo (Transcript 6, page 6, lines 270-272)	Teachers even sacrifice and do extra effort just like trilingual approach in teaching.	
	Teachers extending effort and services just to teach these learners	

P3 shared that she noticed improvements in the learners as she guided them through their writing activities. P4 added that when they had essay tasks, he provided all the necessary details, so the learners only needed to fill in their personal information. He even translated the content to help them understand better.

Parang yong nakasanayan tapos sabi ko para ako lang man ang gasagot dyan sa inyong ano ba pero at least may improvement daily may makikita ka namang improvement ay naka construct siya ng ganoong ano ng sentence ng yan pala yong tinatanong niya kanina (Participant 3, pages 5-6, lines 217-220)

uhh details, naka... ano nagid naka... daw ang isulat nila ang ila information ba... Itagalogon mo pa na kay hindi nila na maintindihan kay nag nag prepare na sila sang papel ahh.. ano yan sir da katiig sir di di namin yan alam ang ahh.. my name is ahh.. ganito ganyan oh anong pangalan nyo name (Participant 4, page 3, lines 81-84)

P4 also added doing spoon feeding in teaching, P5 emphasized that learning may not solely but is highly dependent on the effort of teachers as they lack necessary learning resources, and P6 also shared having sacrifices as a teacher to Manobo, making extra effort in translating, and even extending teaching services just to impart knowledge with these learners.

ana daw spoon-feeding kung sobra pa sa spoon-feeding ana gid man. (Participant 4, page 3, lines 85-86)

sa mga far-flung schools din naman kasi talaga, we lack resources. So... ang masasabi ko is it's upon the teacher na rin talaga to do the effort no (Participant 5, page 2, lines 44-45)

It it's upon the effort of the teacher and sa interest pa rin talaga ng bata (Participant 5, page 3, lines 85-86)

so ikaw na teacher... sacrifice ka talaga.. gagawin mo lahat kahit na yong mga approach na hindi na ginagamit sa DepEd..gagawin mo kasi halimbawa yong triling trilingual approach (Participant 6, page 2, lines 69-70)

So ang ginagawa namin na noon, during that time pa, gumawa kami ng bahay jan sa school, to in order to house yung mga malalayo, so pag-gabi gin tutoran na siya, yung mga...mga mga mga lagyo (Transcript 6, page 6, lines 270-272)

Teachers in ELT for Manobo learners go above and beyond, from guiding writing tasks and translating materials into three languages to offering personalized support. Their dedication reflects a deep desire to help learners understand and grow (Suganob & Bacus, 2023).

Subtheme 5. Teachers' long-term goal for Manobo learners

Teachers often look beyond immediate academic outcomes and envision a brighter future for their Manobo students—one that includes greater opportunities, stronger communication skills, and empowerment through education.

Table 31. Excerpts on Teachers' long-term goal for Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on purposeful teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
<p>long term... gusto ko... may ano... may gusto ko para sa ila na ten years, five years from now may ara na isa ka... Manobo nga English Major... no... kaya kahit papano saakon. Maka... may ma... abot lang na siguro nga time... ma... from my student nga ma.. mainspire sa akon as maka ang kwaon nila kay na ispire sya saakon... siguro that's the ano... most... mga ano... nga gina aspire ko nga long term. (Participant 4, page 8, lines 289-293)</p>	<p>Teacher aspire Manobo students to become an English teacher. He wants his learners to be inspired of him and be one someday.</p>	<p>a. Teachers' long-term goal for Manobo learners are shown in desire for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Manobo learner to become English teacher someday • The need of a Manobo teacher coming from their own community
<p>samantala kung mga llonggo ang ilagay diyan how many years pa yan bago makaadjust in terms of learning their language mahirap tulad ko na ngayon hindi pa ako fluent na 12 years na ako hamakon mo na hahaha so yan ang nakikita ko na ano kailangan talaga. (Participant 6, page 4, lines 167-170)</p>	<p>Teacher expresses having difficulty in adjusting with the learners' first language seeing the need for Dulangan Manobo teachers.</p>	<p>b. Teachers aspire for a Manobo teacher coming from their community because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is difficult to adjust with the Manobo language • Non-IP teachers will likely transfer
<p>Kami mga passer by lang kami dito ng mga katsila tawag nila sa amin, mga ilonggo. Hindi kami makasustain, noh, hindi kami makasustain dito sabi ng, sabi ko sa kanila. Ehh, try to encourage the learners na, study well, so that ah someday, they will be the one to teach in this community, in your community (Participant 6, page 8, lines 356-359)</p>	<p>Teacher aspires that someday a Manobo learner will become a teacher in their community because teachers like them will likely transfer</p>	

A common aspiration among these educators is to eventually see a Manobo teacher emerge from the very community they serve, someone who can continue the work with deeper cultural understanding and lasting impact as mentioned by P4 and P6.

long term... gusto ko... may ano... may gusto ko para sa ila na ten years, five years from now may ara na isa ka... Manobo nga English Major... no... kaya kahit papano saakon. Maka... may ma... abot lang na siguro nga time... ma... from my student nga ma.. mainspire sa akon as maka ang kwaon nila kay na inspire sya saakon... siguro that's the ano... most... mga ano... nga gina aspire ko nga long term. (Participant 4, page 8, lines 289-293)

Kami mga passer by lang kami dito ng mga katsila tawag nila sa amin, mga ilonggo. Hindi kami makasustain, noh, hindi kami makasustain dito sabi ng, sabi ko sa kanila. Ehh, try to encourage the learners na, study well, so that ah someday, they will be the one to teach in this community, in your community (Participant 6, page 8, lines 356-359)

They aspire to have a Manobo teacher coming from the Manobo community because it is difficult to adjust with the Manobo language even when exposed for a long period of time and the fact that these non-IP teachers will eventually seek for transfer someday.

samantala kung mga Ilonggo ang ilagay diyan how many years pa yan bago makaadjust in terms of learning their language mahirap tulad ko na ngayon hindi pa ako fluent na 12 years na ako hamakon mo na hahaha so yan ang nakikita ko na ano kailangan talaga. (Participant 6, page 4, lines 167-170)

Teachers often hold hopes that extend beyond the classroom. For those teaching Manobo learners, a key aspiration is to see a student from the community become an English teacher, equipped with cultural understanding and linguistic ease. As Cabal (2017) noted, this goal is particularly important due to the challenges non-IP teachers face, such as language barriers and high turnover, making it essential to raise educators from within the community.

IX. Resilient Teaching

Figure 11. Schematic Diagram on Resilient Teaching

Resilient teaching in English Language Teaching to Manobo learners means being strong and dedicated despite challenges. It involves flexibility in handling Manobo learners and showing patience in handling Manobo learners. Teachers also show resilience by embracing these Manobo learners and showing compassion in ELT to Manobo learners. This includes making adjustment in handling Manobo learners and working to develop commitment with your job. Even though ELT to Manobo is challenging, resilient teachers continue with hope, care, and determination.

Subtheme 1. Flexibility in Handling Manobo Learners

Teaching English to Manobo learners requires teachers to slow down, listen more, and adapt. With students coming from diverse language and cultural backgrounds, lessons don't always go as planned—and that's perfectly fine. Over time, teachers develop greater patience and flexibility, finding new ways to connect and communicate effectively. This experience is both humbling and rewarding, enhancing their teaching skills.

Table 32. Excerpts on Flexibility in handling Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
Siguro kua...yong you need to be ... kung yong sabi nila na ... flexible kung may other term pa siguro don maam..... yon pa siguro yong gagamitin ko mas kwan pa gid sa flexible sa lahat ng flexible kasi you need to... deal with your learner eh... (Participant 1, page 2, lines 62-64). flexible (Participant 1, page 6, lines 225).	Teacher expresses the need for flexibility or even more when dealing with your learners Be flexible as an English language teacher to Manobo	a. Flexibility of teachers in handling Manobo learners as teachers shared: • Flexibility is needed in teaching them • Being flexible as a teacher to them
ahhh, flexible, flexibility... (Participant 2, page 6, line 238).	Be flexible	

P1 and P2 spoke about flexibility not as a strategy, but as a way of understanding where Manobo learners are coming from to appropriately deal with them. They adjusted their teaching by listening closely to what is within the community, sometimes slowing down lessons, sometimes switching languages, always responding to what students needed that day. For them, resilient teaching meant being present, not just prepared.

These insights align with findings from Bishop and Durksen (2020), who highlighted that effective engagement with Indigenous students requires teachers to possess personal attributes such as patience, flexibility, and empathy. Their research underscores the importance of these qualities in building trust and enhancing educational outcomes for Indigenous learners.

Subtheme 2. Patience in Handling Manobo Learners

Patience is a crucial aspect of resilient teaching, especially when working with Manobo learners who may face unique cultural and academic challenges. By exercising patience, teachers can create a supportive environment that allows these students to thrive at their own pace and feel respected in their learning journey.

Table 33. Excerpts on Patience in handling Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
be patient? (Participant 1, page 6, lines 223).	Be patient as an English language teacher to Manobo	a. Patience of teachers in handling Manobo learners as evident in the teachers' sharing:
Pasensiya din talaga... (Participant 1, page 6, lines 239).	Be patient	• Be patient
magkaroon ng pasensya ganon maam (Participant 2, page 6, line 223)	An English teacher to Manobo learners must have patience	• An English to them must be patient
grabi ang patience mo eh (Participant 3, page 9, line 378)	Great amount of patience is needed	• Have a great deal of patience
you have to have mgaaaa pila ka miles ngaa patience gid. Hindi gid pwede ngaaaa ano ka, impatient ka hindi ka gid pwede sa ila (Participant 3, page 10, lines 386-387)	Have a great deal of patience. Impatient teachers are not suitable with these learners	• Teacher remains patient
nong parang ang patience ko mahaba pa rin ganoon... (Participant 5, page 2, line 75)	Teacher remains patient	• Lengthening of patience
but lengthen your patience (Participant 5, page 6, lines 240-241)	Teacher shared on lengthening patience.	• Develop patience
na develop na shape yong ano mo yong motivation mo na...toteach ah to have more patience in dealing with these ahh learners kasi kong ...isa ka supot lang ang imo nga patience kulang na siya dapat sako sako gid na patience kasi pagkulang yang patience sa pagtuturo na mga tribo itong na mga learners na ito..you will really seek for transfer hindi mo talaga kakayanin ako naka sustain ako for 12 years (Participant 6, page 2, lines 63-67)	You will eventually develop patience in teaching these tribal learners—otherwise, you might find yourself seeking a transfer.	• Needs a lot or great deal of patience
at nasabi ko nga kanina it needs a lot of patience to cater and to teach English language (Participant 6, page 7, lines 315-317)	It needs a lot of patience.	b. Patience of teachers in handling Manobo learners is needed due to:
hindi ka maka deliver sang medium speaking hindi mo man intindihan ang language nila at the same time hindi ka man nila maintindihan so budlay so kung wala ka pasensya sina amuna gid nang matabo mag transfer ka gid. (Participant 6, page 10, lines 442-445)	Teacher finds it difficult to communicate with them due to language barrier, so patience is needed otherwise you will seek for transfer	• Impatient teachers are not for them
		• Avoid transfer of school
		• Difficulty in communicating with the learners due to language gap
		• Otherwise, teacher will seek for transfer

Almost all the participants mentioned patience as one of the teaching qualities that must be possessed by a teacher handling Manobo learners.

Pasensiya din talaga... (Participant 1, page 6, lines 239).

magkaroon ng pasensya ganon maam (Participant 2, page 6, line 223)

grabi ang patience mo eh (Participant 3, page 9, line 378)

but lengthen your patience (Participant 5, page 6, lines 240-241)

at nasabi ko nga kanina it needs a lot of patience to cater and to teach English language (Participant 6, page 7, lines 315-317)

P3 also added that impatient teachers could not teach these kind of learners.

you have to have mgaaaa pila ka miles ngaa patience gid. Hindi gid pwede ngaaaa ano ka, impatient ka hindi ka gid pwede sa ila (Participant 3, page 10, lines 386-387)

This has been intensified by P6 saying that patience is needed to sustain in teaching Manobo learners. He even noted that a teacher will most likely seek transfer if not because of patience. This has helped him to continue teaching Manobo learners for 12 years.

na develop na shape yong ano mo yong motivation mo na...toteach ah to have more patience in dealing with these ahh learners kasi kong ...isa ka supot lang ang imo nga patience kulang na siya dapat sako sako gid na patience kasi pagkulang yang patience sa pagtuturo na mga tribo itong na mga learners na ito..you will really seek for transfer hindi mo talaga kakayanin ako naka sustain ako for 12 years (Participant 6, page 2, lines 63-67)

hindi ka maka deliver sang medium speaking hindi mo man intindihan ang language nila at the same time hindi ka man nila maintindihan so budlay so kung wala ka pasensya sina amuna gid nang matabo mag transfer ka gid. (Participant 6, page 10, lines 442-445)

Bishop and Durksen (2020) emphasize that effective engagement with Indigenous students relies on teachers demonstrating patience, as one of the key personal attributes. Their research highlights how patience is essential in building trust and improving educational outcomes for Indigenous learners.

Subtheme 3. Embracing these Manobo Learners

Embracing Manobo learners goes beyond physical presence or mere acceptance in the classroom. It means opening one's heart to love them genuinely, taking time to adjust to their unique backgrounds, adapting strategies to meet their cultural and

learning needs, and studying their context to provide meaningful and inclusive instruction.

Table 34. Excerpts on Embracing these Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
then learn to love... your...aside from your work, your...yung kuan client, client mo, yung bata mo. (Participant 1, page 6, lines 240).	Learn to love your work and your learners	a. Embracing these Manobo learners through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loving your work and them • Adapting to them • Studying them as learners • Adjusting and adapting to these learners
adapt nila and ma love nila na ayun na eh... (Participant 2, page 6, line 221)	Adapt and love these learners	
So ganun sya, tapos although kami na ano non-IP teachers, ginaorient inoorient din kami to learn and adjust to adapt their way of life probably. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 71-72)	Teacher is informed to learn, to adjust, and to adapt to her learner's context	
and love them (Participant 5, page 6, lines 243-244)	Loving their learners	

P1 and P5 emphasized loving your job and your learners. P2 and P3 mentioned about adapting and studying these learners in order to provide their learning needs.

then learn to love... your...aside from your work, your...yung kuan client, client mo, yung bata mo. (Participant 1, page 6, lines 240).

adapt nila and ma love nila na ayun na eh... (Participant 2, page 6, line 221)

So ganun sya, tapos although kami na ano non-IP teachers, ginaorient inoorient din kami to learn and adjust to adapt their way of life probably. (Participant 3, page 2, lines 71-72)

and love them (Participant 5, page 6, lines 243-244)

Embracing Manobo learners starts with loving both your work and the students you teach. It means being open to learning about who they are, how they learn, and what matters to them. As Gay (2010) shares, good teaching includes respecting the culture of every student and using that as a strength in the classroom. In the end, teaching the Manobo is not just about lessons—it's about building relationships, showing care, and growing together.

Subtheme 4. Compassion in ELT to Manobo Learners

Teaching English to Manobo learners requires more than just delivering lessons. It's a process of developing deep empathy and understanding. Teachers quickly realize

that compassion is vital in adapting to the unique needs of these learners, and this compassion becomes key to fostering effective learning.

Table 35. Excerpts on Compassion in ELT to Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
kumbaga ano gani tawag na maam ah yung iunderstand kung may mga something like yung sa words gud nila maam eh understand na yun hindi nila malitok yung R yun... (Participant 2, page 6, lines 222-223)	Understanding the weaknesses of Manobo learners in ELT	a. Compassion in ELT to Manobo learners through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding their weaknesses • Reaching out to them • Empathy for them
so try to reach reach them out ireach them out ireach mo gid talaga, talaga yung bata kausapin mo talaga kausapin mo sila what's the problem (Participant 3, page 7, lines 266-267)	Teacher reaches out to her learners to address learning problems	b. Teachers' compassion is needed because: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These learners have complex mindsets • They work and play at the same time
nilagay ko ang sarili ko sa kanila noh, "what if ganito ako" (Participant 4, page 1, line 24)	Teacher puts himself in the students' situation	
... kasi itong mga bata na ito nasa ano sila... yung mind set ng mga bata na Dulangan, napakacomplex no nagawork sila the same mahilig sila maglaro the same time mag-aaral pa sila no. So iba-iba yung, lifestyle na pagsinabi mo sa lifestyle nila saka ways of living nila hindi tulad sa atin na kung halos palang hindi ta paobrahon bata ta (Participant 6, page 7, lines 317-321)	Teacher shared on the complex mindset of these learners, saying they are working and playing at the same time since they are still young	

P2, P3, and P4 showed compassion with these learners through understanding their weaknesses, reaching out to them, and having empathy for Manobo learners.

kumbaga ano gani tawag na maam ah yung iunderstand kung may mga something like yung sa words gud nila maam eh understand na yun hindi nila malitok yung R yun... (Participant 2, page 6, lines 222-223)

so try to reach reach them out ireach them out ireach mo gid talaga, talaga yung bata kausapin mo talaga kausapin mo sila what's the problem (Participant 3, page 7, lines 266-267)

nilagay ko ang sarili ko sa kanila noh, "what if ganito ako" (Participant 4, page 1, line 24)

Teachers' compassion is essential because these learners have complex mindsets—they are already familiar with responsibilities, some are working to help their parents at a young age, and naturally, they still want to play and enjoy their childhood. This is evident in the statement of P6.

... kasi itong mga bata na ito nasa ano sila... yung mind set ng mga bata na Dulangan, napakacomplex no nagawork sila the same mahilig sila maglaro the same time mag-aaral pa sila no. So iba-iba yung, lifestyle na pagsinabi mo sa lifestyle nila saka ways of living nila hindi tulad sa atin na kung halos palang hindi ta paobrahon bata ta (Participant 6, page 7, lines 317-321)

Showing compassion in teaching English to Manobo learners means more than just helping them learn a language—it means understanding their background, listening to their stories, and being patient with their pace. Compassion allows teachers to connect on a deeper level, creating a safe space where learners feel accepted and encouraged. When teachers show kindness and genuine care, it builds trust and confidence, making learning more meaningful. As Oxford (2016) points out, compassionate teaching supports not only academic growth but also emotional well-being. With compassion, ELT becomes a bridge between cultures and a tool for empowerment.

Subtheme 5. Adjustment in Handling Manobo Learners

For non-IP teachers, adjustment is necessary when teaching Manobo learners who may have a different way of thinking, learning, and understanding the world. These students come from a unique culture, and their experiences may not always match what is commonly taught in school.

Table 36. Excerpts on Adjustment in Handling Manobo learners as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
...nag adjust din talaga... (Participant 1, page 2, line 82).	Teacher shares about adjusting in ELT to Manobo learners	Adjustment in handling Manobo learners as teachers shared:
ahh major adjustment siya kasi nga ahh ako, hindi man ako ako IP IP teacher, I mean IP,.... IP yung aking ethnicity, so ang laking adjustment sa akin... (Participant 3, page 1, lines 11-12)	Major adjustment for non-IP teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjusting with them • Major adjustment with them • Adjustment due to their way of thinking
tapos medyo iadjustment kayyy, ibaaa ang thinking nila sa aton (Participant 3, page 9, line 378)	Adjustment as teachers due to learners' way of thinking	
So kailangan major adjustment (participant 4, page 10, line 386)	Teachers' adjustment	

P3 and P4 shared that being a teacher in a Manobo community led them to major adjustments such as teachers need to adjust how they speak, explain lessons, and relate to their students.

Adjusting to the needs of Manobo learners means meeting them where they are—with respect and an open heart. It's about understanding that they have different ways of learning, communicating, and seeing the world. As teachers, we must respond with sensitivity and care. These adjustments in our teaching methods, materials, and classroom routines build trust and make learning meaningful. Villaluz and Garvida (2019) emphasize that non-Indigenous teachers must adjust their approaches to effectively reach Indigenous students. By making these thoughtful adjustments, we create a classroom where Manobo learners truly belong.

Subtheme 6. Develop Commitment with your Job

Teaching English to Manobo learners deepens a teacher's sense of commitment. It reminds educators that their role goes beyond the classroom—they are helping preserve hope, build confidence, and open opportunities. This kind of teaching asks for more than skill; it calls for dedication, consistency, and a genuine heart for the learners' growth.

Table 37. Excerpts on Develop commitment with your job as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
So pag sabi ko pag halimbawa magkasakit ako tapos sabi ko pano ning mga estudyante wala na sila may makuha sa akon. So parang every day is learning day for for them. (Participant 3, page 8, lines 305-307)	Teacher thinks about the learning these learners must be getting despite personal challenges like being sick	Develop commitment with their job as they: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think about the learners' learning despite being sick • Stay diligent despite difficulty in teaching • Acknowledges everything as part of the job • Seeks growth as a teacher • Motivates himself to keep doing his job • Strengthen your purpose as a teacher due to learners' situation
kahit mahirap daw silang turuan...diligent parin daw ako... (Participant 5, page 2, line 74)	Even if teaching them is hard, teacher stays diligent	
eh sabi ko naman e trabaho lang go lang.. oo..ahhh well it's all part of the job... (Participant 5, page 2, lines 75-76)	Teacher noted that it is all part of his job	
I think, as an English Teacher, nangangalawang na ako.. oo. So that's why, even now na nag-aattend ako ng seminars (Participant 5, page 5, lines 178-179)	Attending of seminars to gear up teaching skills	
and just do your job, do your job (Participant 5, page 6, lines 243-244)	Keep on doing your job as a teacher	
yong purpose mo as a teacher kasi itong mga tribo na ito ito yong mga na left behind kawawa ba... (Participant 6, page 2, lines 68-69)	ELT to Manobo learners will strengthen your purpose as a teacher because of the learners' unfortunate situation	

Teachers are committed in English language teaching to Manobo learners as evident in their responses. P3 shared that she still thinks about her learners despite being sick because they will not learn without her.

So pag sabi ko pag halimbawa magkasakit ako tapos sabi ko pano ning mga estudyante wala na sila may makuha sa akon. So parang every day is learning day for for them. (Participant 3, page 8, lines 305-307)

P5 also added on staying diligent in teaching despite the struggles while also acknowledging that everything is part of his job and that he aspires to continually grow as a teacher.

kahit mahirap daw silang turuan...diligent parin daw ako... (Participant 5, page 2, line 74)

eh sabi ko naman e trabaho lang go lang.. oo..ahhh well it's all part of the job... (Participant 5, page 2, lines 75-76)

I think, as an English Teacher, nangangalawang na ako.. oo. So that's why, even now na nag-aattend ako ng seminars (Participant 5, page 5, lines 178-179)

P6 also agreed with that statement and noted that this journey of ELT to Manobo will surely strengthen your purpose as a teacher because of the learners' unfortunate situation.

and just do your job, do your job (Participant 5, page 6, lines 243-244)

yong purpose mo as a teacher kasi itong mga tribo na ito ito yong mga na left behind kawawa ba... (Participant 6, page 2, lines 68-69)

This aligns with Gupta et al. (2019), who stress that teacher commitment, especially in under-resourced and Indigenous communities, involves not just professional effort but personal sacrifice. Their study shows that teachers in these environments demonstrate extraordinary perseverance, which is essential for creating lasting educational change.

Subtheme 7. ELT to Manobo is Challenging

Teaching English to Manobo learners brings many tough challenges for teachers. Language gaps, cultural differences, and unique learning needs make this work hard. Teachers often feel stuck when usual teaching methods do not work well. These real struggles make resilient teaching a must. When things get tough, teachers need the strength to keep trying, change their methods, and stay hopeful. The many challenges in teaching English to Manobo students show why teacher resilience matters so much.

Table 38. Excerpts on ELT to Manobo is challenging as one of the subthemes on resilient teaching

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Theme Cluster
it's a big challenges (Participant 1, page 6, lines 203).	Teacher shares that ELT to Manobo comes with big challenges	Resilient teaching needed because ELT to Manobo is challenging as teachers described it as:
super challenging, its super challenging talaga kasi... you cannot ano, you cannot push what you really (Participant 5, page 4, lines 164-165)	It is very challenging due to difficulty in transferring knowledge	
nanibago talaga ako doon kasi hindi mo ma deliver yung lesson instruction mo, means of instruction mo sa mga bata especially pag instruction mo mag activity ka mahirap hindi nila makuha... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 16-18)	It is hard since you cannot directly talk to them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With big challenging • Has difficulty in transferring knowledge • Hard because you cannot directly talk to your learners
Ito lang talaga ang word na mai-ukol no dito sa teaching English sa Dulangan Manobo, ah hard at saka challenging... (Participant 6, page 7, lines 315-317)	Teachers describes ELT to Manobo as hard and challenging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard and challenging

P1 and P6 describe ELT to Manobo as very challenging.

it's a big challenges (Participant 1, page 6, lines 203).

super challenging, its super challenging talaga kasi... you cannot ano, you cannot push what you really (Participant 5, page 4, lines 164-165)

P6 also experienced feeling out of place during his early years in teaching English to Manobo learners because he cannot directly talk or deliver instructions to his learners.

nanibago talaga ako doon kasi hindi mo ma deliver yung lesson instruction mo, means of instruction mo sa mga bata especially pag instruction mo mag activity ka mahirap hindi nila makuha... (Participant 6, page 1, lines 16-18)

Ito lang talaga ang word na mai-ukol no dito sa teaching English sa Dulangan Manobo, ah hard at saka challenging... (Participant 6, page 7, lines 315-317)

When teaching becomes hard, that is when resilience is needed. This is something that is embodied by these teachers since they were able to continue imparting knowledge to these learners. This resilience in the face of educational challenges is crucial, as teachers must adapt to adversity, recover from negative experiences, and thrive despite ongoing difficulties (Mansfield et al., 2016).

Essence of English Language Teaching to Manobo Learners

This part presents the essence of the lived experience of English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners. By examining the nine (9) core themes and their associated subthemes from participant interviews, this analysis reveals the fundamental structure of this educational phenomenon in three emergent themes. The three emergent themes are: 1. Manobo Learners Learning English Language, 2. English Teachers Teaching English to Manobo Learners, and 3. Teachers' Aspirations.

1. Manobo Learners Learning English Language

Table 39. Manobo learners learning English language as the emergent theme for themes I, II, and III

Themes	Emergent Theme
Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers	Manobo learners learning English language
Learners' Context as characterized by teachers	
Significant Encounters of teachers in the journey of ELT to Manobo	

In the context of English Language Teaching (ELT) to Manobo learners, emergent theme 1. Manobo Learners Learning English Language highlights the core realities that shape the educational experience of Manobo learners. From Theme I – Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers, socioeconomic, geographical, and cultural challenges all influence how Manobo learners engage with English. Teachers also observed that teaching takes more time than usual, showing that these barriers slow the pace of instruction. These challenges not only affect access but also reflect deep structural issues that require understanding and patience. As Lumontod and Pradia (2023) emphasize, the best way to win a battle is to study your enemies, just as teachers must know their learners in order to do the job well.

This insight is further emphasized in Theme II – Learners' Context as characterized by teachers, where factors like limited English exposure, absence of phonetic sounds from L1, and learners' slow learning pace become more evident. Teachers also noted low retention, which calls for adaptive strategies and sustained support. These realities show that language learning is not just about instruction—it is about knowing your learners and adjusting to their cognitive abilities. According to Gay (2010), effective teaching depends on understanding the context and individual needs of learners, ensuring that educators tailor their approach to what students can grasp and apply.

Despite the challenges, teachers also shared positive experiences in Theme III – Significant encounters of teachers in ELT to Manobo learners. They noted the positive attitude of Manobo learners, the rewarding two-way language exchange, and positive experiences in the learning journey. Teachers also acknowledged the positive nature of the Manobo tribe, reinforcing the importance of understanding and connecting with learners on a deeper level. These encounters show the importance of knowing your

learners. It is only when teachers truly know their learners that they can build meaningful connections that lead to better outcomes. As Lumontod and Pradia (2023) argue, knowing your learners is central to overcoming challenges and fostering success in teaching.

2. English Teachers Teaching English to Manobo Learners

Table 40. English teachers teaching English to Manobo learners as the emergent theme for themes IV, V, and VI

Themes	Emergent Theme
Effective teaching strategies for Manobo learners	English teachers teaching English to Manobo learners
Culturally responsive teaching	
Resourcefulness in remote teaching	

In the second emergent theme, 2. English Teachers Teaching English to Manobo Learners, teachers demonstrate strong, grounded practices that reflect both responsiveness and practicality in their current teaching environment. This shows how teachers assigned in Manobo communities has faced this journey of ELT. This is clearly seen in Theme IV – Effective Teaching Strategies, where teachers apply consistency in teaching a concept, make use of rewards, and create engaging teaching activities that support cooperative learning. These strategies are not simply routine; they show a thoughtful effort to meet learners where they are and keep them involved in the learning process. As Tortola (2024) notes, effective teaching in multicultural and rural contexts often depends on adapting classroom strategies to maintain clarity, motivation, and student engagement.

Alongside effective strategies, teachers also show deep cultural sensitivity through Theme V – Culturally Responsive Teaching in ELT to Manobo learners. They recognize that ELT to Manobo requires translation, that it needs cultural consideration, and that it should be learner-based. These practices reflect a deep respect for the learners' identity, language, and lived experience. Rather than imposing a one-size-fits-all method, teachers adjust to what's meaningful for Manobo learners. As Hammond (2015) emphasizes, culturally responsive teaching requires educators to align instruction with students' cultural backgrounds and to make learning personally relevant—a clear pattern seen in this theme.

Lastly, Theme VI – Resourcefulness in Remote Teaching shows how teachers maximize what they have to deliver quality education despite limitations. They rely on pictures, audio-visual materials, and local resources to enhance English learning for Manobo students. These efforts show more than creativity—they show commitment. Teachers do not wait for ideal conditions; they adapt with care and determination. As Tortola (2024) observes, resourcefulness in low-resource contexts is a mark of teacher resilience and professionalism, especially when driven by a belief in learners' potential. Together, these themes illustrate how effective, culturally responsive, and resourceful teaching are essential for inclusive and impactful ELT in indigenous communities.

3. Teachers' Aspirations

Table 41. Teachers' aspirations as the emergent theme for themes VII, VIII, and IX

Themes	Emergent Theme
Effective teaching strategies for Manobo learners	Teachers' aspirations
Culturally responsive teaching	
Resourcefulness in remote teaching	

The emergent theme, 3. Teachers' Aspirations brings together what truly drives educators—the emotional and personal connections they form with their learners. From Theme VII – Teachers' Motivation in Teaching, teachers expressed fulfillment in learners' progress and appreciation, showing that their motivation is rooted in care and a deep sense of responsibility. These affective experiences shape their long-term goals and energize their daily work. As Willis (2021) points out, teachers' aspirations are often built on emotional rewards, not just academic outcomes.

This heart-driven commitment is also seen in Theme VIII – Purposeful Teaching in ELT to Manobo learners, where teachers strive to emphasize the importance of learning English, encourage learners, and serve as the key to English learning for Manobo learners. Their extra effort and long-term goals reflect a teaching practice that is guided by meaning and purpose. These actions show that teaching is not just about delivering content but about nurturing potential—especially in indigenous and underserved communities. According to Savage et al. (2021), purposeful teaching emerges when educators align their personal values with their instructional goals, creating a more meaningful experience for both teacher and student.

Finally, Theme IX – Resilient Teaching in ELT to Manobo learners shows how teachers remain dedicated even in difficult conditions. They practice flexibility, patience, compassion, and adjustments while continuing to embrace their learners. Despite acknowledging that ELT to Manobo is challenging, they demonstrate a strong sense of commitment. This resilience is not just a survival skill—it's part of a broader aspiration to make a difference. As Gupta et al. (2019) argue, resilience in teaching is closely linked to emotional engagement and the capacity to stay grounded in one's mission. Together, these three themes highlight that Teachers' Aspirations are shaped by emotional connection, purposeful action, and a commitment to keep going, even when the path is not easy.

Insights

Through this research, the researcher has come to know that in ELT to Manobo learners both teachers and students are learning from each other since teachers become familiar to the language of Manobo learners as time passes by. Also, the researcher has realized how this teaching situation could improve the teaching qualities of a teacher as they lengthen their patience and become deeply committed in their job. Their dedication goes beyond just teaching English—it involves adjustment, and personal sacrifice. Teachers do not simply follow a curriculum; they adjust their methods to fit the needs of

their students, often with limited resources and training (Gay, 2018). This shows that teaching is not just about knowledge transfer but about promoting meaningful connections with students.

Another key insight is that culturally responsive teaching plays a major role in making ELT more effective for Manobo learners. Teachers who respect and integrate the students' native language and culture into their lessons help learners feel more engaged and confident (Freeman & Freeman, 2011). This means that Indigenous education should not only focus on English proficiency but also on making students feel valued and understood in their learning journey.

Lastly, the researcher has come to appreciate the resilience and purposeful teaching of teachers that these communities must have. Many face challenges such as lack of materials, diverse learners, and even geographic isolation, yet they continue to teach with passion and commitment (Day, 2004). This made the researcher reflect on how important it is to support these teachers—not just with resources, but also with training and motivation.

Conclusions

Based on the shared experiences of teachers, nine (9) themes transpired which describe the ELT to Manobo learners. The nine themes are: I. Challenges of learners as perceived and experienced by teachers with four (4) subthemes: Socioeconomic challenges, Geographical challenges, Cultural challenges, and Teaching takes more time than usual; II. Learners' Context as characterized by teachers with also four (4) subthemes: Limited English language exposure, Absence of phonetic sound from L1 causing difficulty in L2, Learners' slow learning pace, and Learners' low retention; III. Significant Encounters of teachers in the journey of English Language Teaching to Manobo learners with six (6) subthemes: Challenging encounters of teachers in ELT to Manobo, Positive attitude of Manobo learners in English language learning, Two-way language exchange between teachers and Manobo, Positive experiences in the English learning journey of Manobo learners, Positive nature of the Manobo tribe, and Opposing views of ELT to Manobo; IV. Effective Teaching Strategies for Manobo learners with four (4) subthemes: Consistency in teaching a concept, Use of rewards, Use of engaging teaching activities, and Cooperative learning; V. Culturally responsive teaching in English Language Teaching to Manobo learners with three (3) subthemes: ELT to Manobo requires translation, ELT to Manobo needs cultural consideration, and Learner-based teaching; VI. Resourcefulness in remote teaching; Maximizing the use of pictures due to limited access to instructional materials, Maximizing the use of audio-visual, Maximizing local resources to enhance English learning among Manobo students; VII. Teachers Motivation in Teaching with two (2) subthemes: Fulfillment in learners' progress, and Fulfillment in learners' appreciation; VIII. Purposeful Teaching with five (5) subthemes: Emphasizing the importance of learning English language, Encourage learners, Teachers as the key to English learning for Manobo learners, Extra effort of teachers in ELT to Manobo, Teachers' long-term goal for Manobo learners; and IX. Resilient Teaching with seven (7) subthemes: Flexibility in handling Manobo learners, Patience in handling

Manobo learners, Embracing these Manobo learners, Compassion in ELT to Manobo learners, Adjustment in handling Manobo learners, Develop commitment with your job and ELT to Manobo is challenging.

The essence of English Language Teaching to Manobo learners is characterized by the three emergent themes. The first emergent theme focuses on Manobo learners learning English language. This part shows how learners are characterized by teachers, what are the experiences of teachers while dealing with these Manobo learners. The second theme highlights English teachers teaching English to Manobo learners. This highlights the actions, strategies, methods, and resources used by teachers as they teach Manobo learners and lastly, the third theme is about Teachers' aspirations, discuss how teachers found deep fulfillment in seeing their students make progress and appreciate their efforts. Knowing that they were the key to their students' learning drove them to put in that extra effort every day. Even though the journey was tough, they demonstrated immense resilience. With patience, flexibility, and compassion, they adapted to the unique needs of Manobo learners, leading to their continued service for these Manobo learners.

Recommendations

To better support ELT teachers in Indigenous communities, the researcher strongly recommends increased access to professional development programs. Many teachers have the passion but lack specialized training in culturally responsive teaching. Workshops, seminars, and even online resources should be provided to help them enhance their skills and adapt their teaching methods more effectively.

Another key recommendation is improving teaching materials and resources such as providing textbooks or dictionaries that has translated words from Manobo to Filipino to English language and vice versa. Many teachers struggle with outdated textbooks or lack of learning tools, which makes teaching English more difficult. Schools and education policymakers should allocate funding to ensure that Indigenous students have access to high-quality, relevant materials that incorporate both English and their native language.

Lastly, the researcher recommends stronger community and government support for Indigenous ELT educators. Their work is demanding, yet they receive little recognition or incentives. Providing higher salaries, mental health support, and incentives for those teaching in remote areas will help keep them motivated and prevent teacher burnout. Supporting teachers ultimately means supporting Indigenous learners, ensuring they receive the education they deserve. The Department of Education should also reinforce their drive for teachers' localization. Manobo education graduates should be encouraged to return in their places to serve their community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Strict adherence to research protocols established by Notre Dame of Marbel University was upheld, ensuring ethical standards were thoroughly observed throughout the research process. The necessary documents from the DepEd Division Office of Sultan

Kudarat and the NDMU Graduate School were obtained prior to commencing the study. Clearance from the NDMU Ethics Review Board was also secured. Measures were implemented to safeguard participants' confidentiality, privacy, and individual rights.

Ethical Considerations is also employed in the text. Lincoln and Guba (1985), as cited by Alexander (2019), identify four fundamental criteria that must be satisfied. The four criteria of Ethical Considerations include: Credibility, Dependability, Transferability, and Confirmability.

For credibility, the researcher assures that the data given by the participants is not manipulated. Also, the data are completely provided, and no information is omitted to skew the results to a desirable outcome. Furthermore, the researcher ensures that the interpretations are free of bias and prejudice amongst and within the participants.

In dependability, the researcher guarantees that the Interview Guide undergoes validation before using it during personal interviews. Also, the results of the thematic analysis is checked by the adviser.

For the confirmability in this study, the researcher makes sure that the transcription is shown to the participants of the study and that it is free from bias.

For transferability, the results of the analysis in this research are limited only to the phenomenon provided, which is the teaching of English to Manobo learners as experienced by teachers but can be applied in related conditions which include and not limited to teaching to indigenous learners.

Transparency is also adhered to in this study. It is worth noting that the researcher does not receive any funding from any sponsor since this study is for academic purposes only. Hence, there is no conflict of interest.

For privacy, confidentiality, and data protection plan, the researcher assures that the identity of the participants and the data collected from participants were not disclosed. Any personal information or data collected from participants were handled with the utmost care and were not disclosed to any unauthorized parties. Participant identities were anonymized using unique codes, and all identifiable information were removed from research reports and publications to ensure privacy. Data collected during this study were securely stored on password-protected devices and encrypted files accessible only to the researcher. Physical documents were stored in a locked file cabinet. All data were retained for a predetermined period as required by ethical guidelines and will be securely destroyed after the completion of this study.

Also, the Informed Consent Form and Participant Agreement Form were given to the participants before conducting the face-to-face interview. These forms contain the necessary information which should be known to the participants. It also indicates the right of the participants to withdraw from the study at any time, and all collected data will be promptly removed upon withdrawal.

This study may impose risk on teachers due to emotional distress, yet this is minimized by ensuring that participation is voluntary and that no sensitive or invasive questions are asked. Participation in this study will add to the scholarly body of work currently on record for the field of education, especially in consideration of the organizational culture of every school.

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institution exceeded expectations. Beyond academic knowledge, the institution taught the researcher values of professionalism, respect, and kindness—principles that will be carried forward in life.

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